

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

DOCTOR OF COMMUNICATION

Eric Alcuezar Fernandez

**Social Media Culture among Automobile Training Industry Associates and
Trainees and Their Performance in the Workplace**

Thesis Adviser:

Dr. Benjamina Paula Gonzalez-Flor
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

27 July 2023

Permission of the classification of this academic work access is subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations:

Invention (I)	☐ Yes or ☒ No
Publication (P)	☐ Yes or ☒ No
Confidential (C)	☐ Yes or ☒ No
Free (F)	☒ Yes or ☐ No

Student's signature:

E Fernandez

Dissertation adviser signature:

B Gonzalez-Flor

University Permission Page

Social Media Culture among Automobile Training Industry Associates and Trainees and Their Performance in the Workplace

"I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this Academic Work in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page."

"I specifically allow the University to:

- a. Upload a copy of the work in the theses database of the college/school/institute/department and in any other databases available on the public internet*
- b. Publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and*
- c. Give open access to the work, thus allowing "fair use" of the work in accordance with the provision of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly and research purposes.*

Eric Alcuezar Fernandez and July 27, 2023
Signature over Student Name and Date

Acceptance Page

This paper prepared by **ERIC ALCUEZAR FERNANDEZ** with the title: “**SOCIAL MEDIA CULTURE AMONG AUTOMOBILE TRAINING INDUSTRY ASSOCIATES AND TRAINEES AND THEIR PERFORMANCE IN THE WORKPLACE**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

DR. BENJAMINA PAULA GONAZALEZ-FLOR
Chair, Dissertation Committee

(Date)

DR. GRACE ALFONSO
Member, Dissertation Committee

(Date)

DR. MELINDA BANDALARIA
Member, Dissertation Committee

(Date)

DR. DIEGO SILANG S. MARANAN

Dean

Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

5 September 2023
(Date)

Biographical Sketch

Eric Alcuezar Fernandez is my name. In Dungguan, Datu Montawal, which used to be part of Pagalungan, Maguindanao, I was born to very humble, unsullied Catholic parents.

I earned a Master of Arts in Development Communication from the University of the Philippines Open University and a Bachelor of Arts in Communication Arts from Ateneo de Davao University. In addition, I received a Master of Arts in Media Studies in TV and Radio Broadcasting from the University of the Philippines Diliman after completing 33 academic units with the exception of my thesis. I am about to graduate from the Doctor of Communication program at the University of the Philippines Open University.

Since December 2000, I have been teaching English as a Second Language (ESL). For approximately ten years, I have taught Korean nationals in the Philippines English. I have been employed as an English instructor for this automobile training industry in Jeddah, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, since 2010 to instruct future Saudi technicians for the Kingdom's Japanese automobile distributors (JADIK). In addition, I have worked as an IELTS coach and Training Officer in two caregiving centers in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. At Integrated Caregiving and Related Expertise Academy (iCARE), I am in charge of the IELTS Preparation, Advanced English Communication Skills, and Basic English Communications for Computer Literacy programs. On the other hand, at Universal Skills Development Institute (USDI), I am in charge of the IELTS Preparation and Basic English Communications for Health Professionals. Under USDI's Caregiver/Nursing Assistant/Healthcare Assistant program, I am currently a full scholar.

I also completed the Professional Teaching Certification (PTC) program at the University of the Philippines Open University, which provides a solid background for my teaching career. Additionally, I took the Special Professional Licensure Board Examination for Teachers in September 2016 after applying for it. It was my first time, and I placed Top 4 overall in the entire region.

While in Jeddah I have a plan of getting Certificate in English Language Teaching to Adults (CELTA). Nevertheless, I have started taking Master of Arts in Education major in Educational Management at Philippine Women's University, yet I have put it on hold to give way to my Doctor of Communication studies.

My ultimate goal is to go back to the Philippines and share my knowledge with fellow Filipinos in due time. I am giving myself less than three years or thereabouts to become financially stable to make my penultimate dream come true.

I love veggies and keeping in shape. In fact, I am keen on weight training.

Acknowledgement

This is something I said in my first book, *Don't Wrong Your English! 1* (DWYE! 1) and my second book, *The Classified Integrants*, which I published; however, I must reiterate this as my informal mantra from that point forward. Without the support, encouragement, and prayers of a select few people who have always been there for me during this life's roller coaster ride, this dissertation would not have been possible.

Without the unreserved love of Arnold Ellores Granado, my ultimate happiness in life, the success of finally overcoming the obstacles could not even have been conceived.

Also, my profuse gratitude to Arnel Justo Bernardino C. Bustamante, Ronald F. Fernandez, Muhamad Yusmar, and Mark Anthony Ramos who have succeeded not only as my regular and strict gym trainers but my go-to persons when it comes to weight training as well.

This recompense does not even suffice for the sacrifices my Ninang (Godmother), my Mamang (mother), my Papang (father) (may you rest in peace), and my utol (brother) made for me to be able to reach the peak of my dreams. Their proper guidance and full support in all forms have led me to where I am exactly right now. I cannot even thank them all enough all my life.

Also, I thank my only two lovable nephews, Bugoy and Neil, whom I want to be the role model to and serve as an inspiration and motivation.

My Lola (Grandma) Lucia and my Popo (Grandpa) Pablo (may you both have long rested in peace), my Auntie Widing, Uncle Pito (may you have rested in peace), my Auntie Virgin, Uncle Jess (may you have rested in peace), my Auntie Bibi and Uncle Boy (may you both have rested in peace), my Auntie Bata and Uncle Teriong

(may you both have rested in peace), my Auntie Langga (may you have rested in peace), my Auntie Nining and Uncle Niyong (may you both have rested in peace), Auntie Perlie, Uncle Pepe (may you have rested in peace), Ate Ador, Kuya Dado (may you have rested in peace), Ate Ping, Ate Lotlot and Kuya Gil, Che, Shine, Ar, Ate Vivian, Jingjing, Jongjong, Jikjik, Gonggong, Bebet, Dibuy, Bintot, Lanyang, Clingcling (may you have rested in peace), Emily (may you have rested in peace), Bonita, Marissa, Thessa, Kimkim, Rise, Baby, Kuya Edwin (may you have rested in peace) and to all my cousins and relatives who are very dear to me, my wholehearted appreciation. Some of them may not be able to witness this, but this is dedicated to them all.

For the unceasing support of my very few close friends who I am most fortunate to have and never stop pushing me to the limits, I cannot thank them all enough.

To whom I receive both constructive criticisms and otherwise in all forms, I also thank you all knowing the fact that without you this book may not be completed and put into reality. I also owe a great deal from all of them.

To my exes who have taught me life lessons no matter how short or long the memories we have shared, allow me to render my requital in this mode.

To my DComm Graduate Advisory Committee, Dr. Grace Alfonso (member), Dr. Melinda Bandalaria (member) and most especially Dr. Benjamina Flor who has always been there to give support and advice round the clock.

Nothing is much greater than relying on the Divine Providence. Above all, He is the one that makes all the things impossible possible if you just fare well in believing in His Power. I never fail to ask His Guidance before I start doing something, and I also never fail to express my gratefulness afterwards. It is always Him who I owe so

much for having had me do things with flying colors and realize that with Him nothing is really impossible.

Dedication

I dedicate this dissertation titled “Social Media Culture among Automobile Training Industry Associates and Trainees and Their Performance in the Workplace” to the following individuals and entities who have been instrumental in my academic journey:

To my lifetime partner, Arnold Ellores Granado and my family, whose unwavering support and encouragement have been the foundation of my success. Your unconditional love, faithfulness and loyalty, belief in me, and sacrifices have motivated me to pursue this research and reach new heights.

To my DComm Graduate Advisory Committee, Dr. Grace Alfonso (member), Dr. Melinda Bandalaria (member) and most especially Dr. Benjamina Flor (chair), for your guidance, expertise, and invaluable insights throughout the dissertation process. Your mentorship has shaped my research and challenged me to think critically, pushing me to produce the best work possible.

To my friends and colleagues, who have provided a network of support, collaboration, and inspiration. Your discussions, brainstorming sessions, and shared experiences have enriched my understanding of social media culture and its implications in the workplace.

To the automobile training industry that granted me access to their valuable resources, data, and participants. Your willingness to collaborate and share insights has been crucial in shaping the findings and conclusions of this research.

To the participants of this study, whose willingness to share their experiences and perspectives has been integral to the validity and richness of the research. Your

contribution has provided valuable insights and helped shed light on the relationship between social media culture and workplace performance.

Above all, to the Divine Providence, whose guidance and blessings have been ever-present throughout my academic journey.

Lastly, I would like to express my gratitude to all those individuals who may not be mentioned here but have played a significant role in my academic journey. Your support, encouragement, and belief in my abilities have been instrumental in reaching this milestone.

This dissertation is dedicated to each and every one of you. Thank you for being a part of my journey and for helping me realize the importance of social media culture in the workplace.

Table of Contents

University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgement	vi
Dedication	ix
Table of Contents	xi
List of Tables	xiii
List of Figures	xiv
ABSTRACT	xvii
CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION	1
Background of the Study	1
Statement of the Problem	4
Objectives of the Study	5
Significance of the Study	6
Scope and Limitations of the Study	7
CHAPTER II: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE	9
CHAPTER III: FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY	34
Conceptual Framework	38
Operational Definition of Terms	40
CHAPTER IV: METHODOLOGY	42
Research Design	42
Research Locale	45
Respondents of the Study	45
Sampling Techniques	45
Research Instrument	47
Instrument Validation	47
Data Gathering Procedure	47
Data Analysis	48
CHAPTER V: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	50
CHAPTER VI: SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS	164
Summary	164
Conclusions	167

Recommendations	170
REFERENCES	173

List of Tables

Table 1 Contingency table 1: Frequency of social media use and commitment in meeting deadlines	143
Table 2 Contingency table 2: Management ability in terms of quantity of work accomplished within a given time	144
Table 3 Contingency table 3: Management ability in terms of quality of work accomplished within a given time	146
Table 4 Contingency table 4: Content sharing with work-related updates and knowledge sharing within the workplace	148
Table 5 Contingency table 5: Content sharing with work-related updates and effective collaboration with colleagues	150
Table 6 Contingency table 6: Content sharing with industry insights and knowledge sharing within the workplace and effective collaboration with colleagues	151
Table 7 Contingency table 7: Content sharing with valuable and knowledge sharing within the workplace and effective collaboration with colleagues	153
Table 8 Contingency table 8: Social media distractions during work hours and staying focused and meeting targets	155
Table 9 Contingency table 9: Efforts putting into developing and maintaining a positive personal brand on social media and reputation within the organization .	157

List of Figures

Figure 1 Participants' profile	51
Figure 2 Frequency of social media use for communication and collaboration	53
Figure 3 Common social media	53
Figure 4 Description of social media culture	54
Figure 5 Effectiveness of social media in promoting diversity and inclusion	54
Figure 6 Extent social media fostered cross-cultural understanding and collaboration	55
Figure 7 Social media enhances cross-cultural communication and collaboration	56
Figure 8 Potential benefits of relying on social media for communication and collaboration	57
Figure 9 Existence of specific social media practices or norms	58
Figure 10 Comfortability to express cultural identity and perspective through social media	60
Figure 11 Observation on social media interaction which led to misunderstanding and cultural conflicts	61
Figure 12 Social media in promoting cultural exchange and knowledge sharing	62
Figure 13 Provision of guidelines on the usage of social media	64
Figure 14 Presence of challenges in social media communication with colleague	65
Figure 15 Social media leverage to celebrate and showcase the diverse cultures and backgrounds within the organization	66
Figure 16 Impact of social media culture on performance and productivity	67
Figure 17 Active engagement on social media translated into real-life action	69
Figure 18 Frequency of action taken on content	70
Figure 19 Motivation of social media users	71
Figure 20 Perception on social media	72
Figure 21 Actions taken by social media users	74
Figure 22 Frequency of online members' active participation in discussions or conversations on social media platforms	75
Figure 23 Extent to which participation on social media platforms translates into tangible actions or outcomes within the organization	77
Figure 24 Members' contribution of innovative ideas or solutions	78
Figure 25 Observation of instances where online members' participation on social media platforms led to the implementation of new projects or initiatives within the organization	79
Figure 26 Effectiveness of online members' participation on social media platforms in driving decision-making processes within the organization	81

Figure 27 Extent to which online members' participation on social media platforms influenced the overall organizational culture and values	82
Figure 28 Differences in the level of action or implementation resulting from online members' participation on social media platforms across different teams or departments within the organization	83
Figure 29 Level of accountability and follow-through	84
Figure 30 Factors contributing to successful translation of online members' participation in social media platforms into meaningful action within the organization	86
Figure 31 Barriers or challenges that hinder the translation of online members' participation on social media platforms into concrete actions or outcomes within the organization	87
Figure 32 Driving action and implementation support	89
Figure 33 Strategies to bridge the gap between online participation in social media platforms and tangible actions	90
Figure 34 Role of effective communication	92
Figure 35 Impact in driving action and achieving organizational goals	94
Figure 36 Improvements and changes	97
Figure 37 Main motivation for the emergence of social media culture	98
Figure 38 Factors for the creation of social media culture	100
Figure 39 Reasons for social media culture influence	102
Figure 40 Impact of social media culture on traditional forms of communication	104
Figure 41 Effect of social media culture emergence	106
Figure 42 Value of the created social media culture to organizational communication.	107
Figure 43 Social media culture contribution to organizational communication	108
Figure 44 Effectiveness of the created social media culture in promoting collaboration and teamwork	110
Figure 45 Degree to which the created social media culture enhanced the accessibility and availability of information	111
Figure 46 Created social media culture facilitated knowledge sharing and dissemination	113
Figure 47 Created social media culture on overall transparency and openness of communication	115
Figure 48 Effectiveness of social media culture in facility of communication across different hierarchical levels within the organization	116
Figure 49 Extent to which the created social media culture encouraged open and constructive feedback exchange	118
Figure 50 Overall impact of the created social media culture on organizational communication	120

Figure 51 Morale aspect	121
Figure 52 Reputation aspect	121
Figure 53 Communication aspect	122
Figure 54 Advertising aspect	122
Figure 55 Collaboration aspect	123
Figure 56 Social research aspect	123
Figure 57 Skill building aspect	124
Figure 58 Transparency aspect	124
Figure 59 Public relation aspect	125
Figure 60 Networking aspect	125
Figure 61 Social media ban	126
Figure 62 Advantages of social media at workplace	129
Figure 63 Disadvantages of social media at workplace	130
Figure 64 Internet usage	132
Figure 65 internet usage: work or work-related	134
Figure 66 Work-related internet usage	134
Figure 67 Frequency in following netiquette guidelines	140
Figure 68 Chart 1: Frequency of social media use and commitment in meeting deadlines	143
Figure 69 Chart 2: Management ability in terms of quantity of work accomplished within a given time	144
Figure 70 Chart 3: Management ability in terms of quality of work accomplished within a given time	146
Figure 71 Chart 4: Content sharing with work-related updates and knowledge sharing within the workplace	148
Figure 72 Chart 5: Content sharing with work-related updates and effective collaboration with colleagues	150
Figure 73 Chart 6: Content sharing with industry insights and knowledge sharing within the workplace and effective collaboration with colleagues	151
Figure 74 Chart 7: Content sharing with valuable and knowledge sharing within the workplace and effective collaboration with colleagues	153
Figure 75 Chart 8: Social media distractions during work hours and staying focused and meeting targets	155
Figure 76 Chart 9: Efforts putting into developing and maintaining a positive personal brand on social media and reputation within the organization	157

Abstract

202 Saudi national trainees and 32 multinational associates at an automobile training industry were participants to examine the association between their social media culture (SMC) and performance.

Cochran's formula with a 95% confidence level and 5 confidence interval was utilized. Generally, all variables were analyzed with chi square and phi coefficient for the frequency distribution and cross tabulation used. Data were gathered through a one-shot survey research design; wherein qualitative methods were employed for triangulation.

In a multicultural organization, it could be inferred that SMC was typically propagated by a combination of factors. It emerged organically among members while organizational policies, leadership support, and communication channels could have shaped and influenced it. The study found out that their participation in SMC translated into tangible actions. In addition, it not only disclosed that the emerging SMC was often created to foster stakeholders' connectivity, knowledge exchange, and engagement, but it also confirmed its added value to organizational communication.

Ultimately anchored with *computer-mediated communication* (CMC) (Walther, 2011), it revealed a slightly moderate direct positive association between SMC shareholders and their workplace performance. This implies that engagement with SMC can have some beneficial effects in a professional setting.

Keywords: communication, social media culture, social media, computer-mediated communication

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Accountable to the fact that social media vis-à-vis technology and different platforms are in constant connection with how it is constituted, which capacitates the content collaboration, exchange, and creation of interactive web by all stakeholders (Cohen, 2011), social media moves on rolling up and its functions shift. This could be one of the contributing factors that interests several researchers about social media ever since it has been in existence after the onset of the internet.

Seaman and Tinti-Kane (2013) aimed to explore and examine the use of social media among individuals using several approaches to investigate and understand, for example, the effects of cultural restrictions on individual' motivation, users' attitude, intention behaviors and their actual use. Seaman and Tinti-Kane (2013) provided insights on the present status of internet usage in some countries and the basis for business and government agencies that may be considered in future development and policy formulation.

Since the advent of the internet, the Saudi government has been very vigilant about what information or sites the users in Saudi could access. Many sites, specifically the ones that promote pornography, have been blocked (Deccan Chronicle, 2016). Likewise, organizations were also keen on social media users at work and went to the extent of even blocking social networking sites (SNS), thinking that it might affect the productivity of the worker.

Up till now, in China, they still implement the Great Firewall, an onerous system that the Chinese government uses to cut off access to, say Gmail from third-party

applications, thereby forcing the Chinese to depend on a virtual private network (V.P.N.) in order to get to their Gmail accounts (Wong, 2015). It can be construed how they are restricted to using SNS while at work when people think these are used only for pastime and can never contribute to the efficacy of the workforce.

Luckily, in most companies now in Saudi, the restrictions on access to any social media have been lifted (Deccan Chronicle, 2016). Employees now enjoy till drop access except for a few, such as in the automobile training industry, where this research was conducted. If any, it is still in the best interest to know various arguments about using social media for communicative processes at work.

This research was prompted by the caprice of some organizations about the imposition of restrictions on the usage of some popular and powerful social media in the workplace. It is interesting to account for the fact that their diminution of social media coverage can sometimes be on and off.

Indeed, the globe is too big to explore, and there are too many resources to look into on the web.

Alsuraihi et al. (2016) examined the social media use in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Alsuraihi et al. (2016) already geared to explore Saudi Arabians' usage of social media, to discover the most common resources used particularly in education and to illustrate students' belief about its influence on their learning.

Seaman and Tinti-Kane (2013) already ventured on several studies in relation to the usage of social media and its impact on employee and organizational performance. However, very few if not none, have ever focused on doing the investigation on the possible correlation between social media culture among the associates and trainees and its effects on their performance in the workplace.

With the existence of social media or SNS, the emergence of social media culture began to surface. Stanford (2016) defined it by breaking it down into three core parts – communication, socialization, and change. He said that these three dimensions continue to exist no matter what social media platform is being used. From the first social media platform, Six Degrees, in 1997 (Stanford, 2016), it was already invented for communication and even up to this date. In the context of socialization, he further stipulated that social media played a more recent important purpose of making individuals learn what is acceptable to social beings. He finally emphasized that while *communication* and *socialization* were essential components of social media, *change* was a by-product. Thereby the propagation of social media culture.

Social media culture is tantamount to the existent digital culture, which is referred to as the knowledge, beliefs, and practices of people having interactions in digital networks that can possibly rebrand tangible-world cultures or engender new strains of both cultural thought and practice associated with digital networks (Poepfel, 2018).

Social media culture has been rapidly evolving since the inception of platforms like YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, and more recently, TikTok. These platforms have become an integral part of people's daily lives, and for many, social media has become an addiction. The impact of social media on culture is undeniable, and this impact is present in social relationships, mental health, politics, entertainment, and more. Suffice to say that in organizations like a school, understanding how social media culture operates could be a valuable contribution to the communication discipline.

There is limited research specifically focusing on the relationship between social media culture among associates and trainees and their performance in the workplace. However, there are some relevant studies that highlight the importance of

social media usage and its impact on employees' performance and behavior in general.

One relevant study by Neubaum, Pagán, and Garcia (2014) examined the effects of social media use on employee productivity and found that excessive use of social media during work hours can lead to reduced productivity. This study emphasizes the need for further investigation into the specific impact of social media culture among associates and trainees on their workplace performance.

Another study by Mesch, Talmud, and Quan-Haase (2012) explored the relationship between employees' social media use and their job satisfaction. The findings indicated that employees who used social media for work-related purposes reported higher job satisfaction. However, this study did not specifically focus on the culture surrounding social media use among associates and trainees, highlighting the need for further research in this area.

Overall, the existing literature provides limited insights into the relationship between social media culture among associates and trainees and their performance in the workplace. Therefore, there is a research gap that needs to be addressed to understand the specific dynamics and impacts of social media culture on the performance of these individuals.

Statement of the Problem

It has been observed over the past decades that social networking allows people to do way more than just communicate status update; however, that is the usual enterprise and the most reason why it is done (Miller, 2011). There is no stopping the proliferation of social media whether in schools, in households, or even in

workplaces. It seems as though having no social networking accounts makes one an outcast.

Even if there is time, there were or probably organizations with backlashes against accepting the idea of social media usage while at work, still SNS managed to sneak out of the scene. At some point firewalls were created to block especially trendy SNSs but eventually people, especially the top management, seemed to accept the role that they play in this digital age.

Usage of SNS particularly Facebook, YouTube, WhatsApp and the like was examined closely to analyze both the social media culture among associates and trainees and both their performance in the workplace.

The study focused on users of Facebook, YouTube, WhatsApp, and other common social media for communicative processes at work and their pros and cons.

Thus, in general, the study attempted to answer the question: How does social media culture among associates and trainees affect their performance in the workplace?

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. How was social media culture created in a multicultural organization?
2. How did the online members' participation translate into action?
3. Why was this emerging culture created? And
4. How will the created social media culture add value to organizational communication?

Objectives of the Study

In general, the study aimed to analyze how social media culture among associates and trainees affects their performance in the workplace.

Specifically, the study attempted to:

1. Describe how social media culture was created in a multicultural organization;
2. Explain how online members' participation translated into action;
3. Analyze how the emerging culture was created; and
4. Examine how the created social media culture can add value to organizational communication.

Significance of the Study

In the context of organizational communication, social media culture could be a new dimension in creating organizational climate. Communication with the use of social media platforms in the 21st century significantly contributes to creating a conducive working environment. Thus, promoting social media for communication and socialization in the workplace where everybody is usually pressed for time and busy could be a new workspace. By even virtually connected, workers can be easily updated of everything since social media is considered a venue for an asynchronous bonding of the workers which can happen 24 hours a day.

This study will also be beneficial to those organizations that still hold restrictions on access to any social media. These organizations probably forget that workers are human beings who need a breather during working hours. By providing workers with some place to unwind, more productivity can even be expected.

Moreover, top management will also benefit from this study since this will provide a justification for their permission to access social media by all workers at work.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The study specifically covered users of Facebook, YouTube, WhatsApp, Instagram, Twitter and other commonly used social media specifically for communicative process in the workplace. Even with roughly three billion monthly active Facebook users as of the second quarter of 2023 (Dixon, 2023), still some do not get to enjoy the opportunity of getting an access not just because of the restrictions but also even having the access to mobile networks was very limited if none at all. This is why associates of this type like the ones in the maintenance department of some companies may not be able to share their valuable perspectives for the study. Moreover, the study may not have been able to access the point of views of associates and trainees who did not have access or simply opt to live a simple life without social media. Likewise, even on extremely opposite situation, the top management's standpoint may not have been taken into consideration as their point of views were very difficult to access like that of the Great Firewall in China.

There was a need to have a reliable interpreter or translator from English to Arabic language since most of the respondents' first language is Arabic. So, there was a need therefore to buy extra time for translating the questionnaire and interview to Arabic to facilitate and make sure the respondents were able to answer each question correctly.

Moreover, this research was geared to uncovering only the probable correlation between the social media culture among associates and trainees and their performance in the workplace of one industry. Inclusion of other industries could have yielded a more reliable association between the variables in study.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Social Media

While social media moves on rolling up and its functions shift and extend, so does how social media is defined. Partly, this is attributed to the fact that social media apropos technology and platforms are in constant connection with how it is constituted and capacitate the interactive web's content creation, collaboration, and exchange by all stakeholders (Cohen, 2011).

Many people have perspectives about how they put meaning to social media. For instance, Rouse (2014) believed that social media is the consortia of online communication channels mainly for community-based input, interaction, content-sharing, and collaboration. Also, it is defined as any highly adaptable and accessible communication tool or method that makes it simple for anyone to influence large groups of people (Blossom, 2009).

Social media can also be called social networks. A social network is a sizable website that houses a community of members and facilitates communication among them (Miller, 2011).

Since they are dubbed as social networks, hence the creation of a network society. The network society is a social formation that has social and media network infrastructure supporting its primary mode of organization at all levels - societal, group/organizational, and even individual (van Dijk, 2006).

Hence, it is also called SNS. SNS will only co-exist with the people that constitute them. They are called netizens. The term netizen was first coined in 1984.

According to Merriam Webster, a netizen is someone who actively utilizes the internet, especially appropriately or acceptably.

Social Media Platforms

At this juncture, the evolution of social media, its effects on culture, and how people interact with it warrants exploration. The introduction of websites like MySpace and LinkedIn in the early 2000s marked the beginning of social media. These platforms were geared towards helping people connect with like-minded individuals, which quickly gained traction. However, they were relatively limited and did not offer the range of features that today's platforms do.

For instance, the introduction of YouTube in 2005 revolutionized how people consumed and shared content (McFadden, 2023). Before YouTube's introduction, sharing videos online was a fragmented and challenging process. YouTube made it easy for individuals to upload and share videos with friends and family. Soon after, Facebook was introduced, and it quickly became the most popular social media platform. Facebook's introduction in 2004 marked a significant turning point for social media, as it was the first platform to offer a range of features, such as photo sharing, messaging, and the ability to create and join groups (Hall, 2023).

Twitter, which is now X, was introduced in 2006, offering a new medium for communication known as microblogging (Britannica, 2023). Its 280-character limit made it easy for people to share quick updates and thoughts with their followers. The platform quickly picked up steam and became a trusted source for news and current affairs (Britannica, 2023).

Snapchat was introduced in 2011, offering a new form of communication known as ephemeral messaging (O'Connell, 2020). Snapchat's stories feature allowed users

to share a series of photos and videos that would disappear after 24 hours. This feature was unique and popular among younger users (O'Connell, 2020).

Most recently, TikTok has taken the world by storm. It was introduced in 2018 and quickly became the most downloaded app in the world (Moore, 2018). TikTok is a short-form video platform that allows users to create and share videos that are 15-60 seconds in length. The platform's algorithm is highly sophisticated, and it was designed to show users content that is likely to be of interest to them.

Social Media Impact on Culture

Social media has had a profound impact on culture. It has changed the way we communicate, consume, and share content and has redefined social norms and behavior (Mohsin, 2022). Here are some of the effects of social media on culture:

1. Social media has altered the way people communicate. It has made it easier to stay in touch with friends and family who live far away. Platforms like Facebook and Instagram allowed individuals to share photos and updates with friends and followers in real time, which has made the world feel smaller and more connected.
2. Social media has led to negative communication habits, such as miscommunication and disconnection. Platforms like Twitter can be a breeding ground for misinterpretation, with users often trolling and misunderstanding each other online. Additionally, because social media allows people to communicate, it can be challenging to disconnect from their devices and, indeed, be present in face-to-face relationships (Mohsin, 2022).
3. Social media has been linked with various mental health issues, such as depression, anxiety, and addiction. It has been found to trigger feelings of

inadequacy and self-doubt as users compare themselves to the carefully curated lives of others online (Mohsin, 2022).

4. Platforms such as Instagram, where users typically share only their best moments, presented a skewed view of reality. Looking at perfectly filtered and edited images can leave users feeling like they do not measure up. Additionally, the constant need to check for notifications can lead to addiction and distractibility.
5. Social media has dramatically impacted politics by serving as a powerful platform for political expression and mobilization (Mohsin, 2022). Platforms like Twitter have become a go-to source for real-time information and informed opinions. Political campaigns and movements can be created with a few clicks of a button, allowing people to make their voices heard and fight for social justice causes.
6. Social media campaigns and movements are often plagued by bots and fake news, which can spread misinformation and push false narratives (source). Additionally, the anonymity of the internet can lead to vicious attacks and dangerous ideologies.
7. Social media has revolutionized the entertainment industry, allowing for new forms of content creation and consumption. Influencers and creators now have massive followings across platforms like TikTok, YouTube, and Instagram, allowing them to monetize their content and achieve fame and success (Mohsin, 2022).
8. The pressure to create viral and sensational content can lead to copycat videos and feed into questionable trends and behaviors. Additionally, the constant scrolling and consuming content can lead to addiction and distractibility (Mohsin, 2022).

9. Social media has become a ubiquitous presence in people's daily lives. The platforms chosen, the accounts followed, and the content consumed shape the social media experience.

Ways in Which People Interact via Social Media

There are some ways people interact with social media. People interact with social media in various ways, depending on their preferences and goals. Here are some common ways people engage with social media:

1. **Creating and sharing content:** Many users create and share their content on social media platforms. This includes posting photos, videos, or written updates about their lives, experiences, and interests. Users often personalize their content by applying filters, captions, or hashtags to make it more appealing or discoverable. Moreover, social media platforms allow users to share information and resources regardless of location (Mao et al., 2011).
2. **Engaging with others' content:** Social media platforms allow users to interact with each other's content through likes, comments, and shares. Users can express their appreciation, offer opinions, ask questions, or provide feedback on posts. This interaction fosters a sense of community and helps users connect with like-minded individuals or communities.
3. **Following and being followed:** Users can follow other users or accounts on social media platforms to stay updated on their activities and content. This allows users to curate their feeds based on their interests and preferences. Being followed by others can provide a sense of validation and influence, especially for influencers or individuals with a large following.

4. **Joining groups or communities:** Many social media platforms offer the option to join or create groups or communities based on specific topics, interests, or goals. These groups provide a space for users to engage in discussions, share relevant content, seek advice, or find support from like-minded individuals. Groups can range from hobby-based communities to professional networking platforms.
5. **Direct messaging and private communication:** Social media platforms often include direct messaging features, enabling users to have private conversations with other users or groups. This feature allows for more intimate and personalized interactions. Users can share information, coordinate plans, seek advice, or engage in conversations that are not meant for public consumption.
6. **Participating in live streams or events:** Many platforms now offer live streaming features where users can broadcast videos in real-time. This enables users to engage with their audience directly, answer questions, or provide live updates. Additionally, social media platforms often host virtual events, webinars, or live chats where users can participate, ask questions, and share insights.
7. **Discovering and exploring content:** Social media platforms use algorithms to recommend content based on users' preferences, behavior, or connections. Users can explore a wide range of content, including news articles, videos, tutorials, or entertainment. Discovering new content allows users to stay informed, entertained, or inspired.
8. **Social activism and awareness:** Social media has become a powerful platform for raising awareness, mobilizing support, and advocating for social and political causes. Users often share information about social issues, participate in online campaigns, sign petitions, or donate to causes they care about. Social media helps amplify voices, facilitates discussions, and creates opportunities for

collective action. Social media platforms can increase engagement and motivation among learners by providing a platform for discussion and debate and by allowing learners to connect with others who share their interests (Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010).

These are just a few ways people interact with social media, and the landscape is continuously evolving as new features and platforms emerge. Ultimately, how individuals engage with social media depends on their personal goals, preferences, and the specific platform they use. These various means would also determine how they behave online.

Active social media consumers frequently engage with content on social media platforms. They create and share content, comment on and like posts, and they have a significant presence on social media. Active consumers are often influencers or creators who monetize their content and have a massive following. They are also users who are regulars on social media platforms, using them as a way to stay connected to friends and family and up to date with news and entertainment (Ingrassia et al., 2022).

Passive social media consumers consume content on social media but do not engage directly with it. They often lurk online, scrolling through feeds and reading posts without liking or commenting. Passive consumers are often people who enjoy using social media for entertainment or informational purposes without feeling the need to participate actively. They may not have a significant presence on social media, but they still consume content on a regular basis (Ingrassia et al., 2022).

Detached social media consumers are those who use social media sparingly or not at all. They are users indifferent to social media and prefer to communicate and connect in other ways. Detached consumers may feel that social media is a waste of

time or that it is detrimental to their mental health. They may prefer to have conversations face-to-face or through other forms of communication and avoid social media altogether.

Social media has transformed how people communicate, consume, and share content and redefined social norms and behavior. The impact of social media on culture is undeniable, and it has both positive and negative effects. As social media continues to evolve, it will be interesting to see how it continues to shape culture and how people interact online or offline.

Almost all human workers these days sit in front of a computer; however, social media did not begin with computers; it emerged on “line” – on the phone. Phone phreaking, or the rascal exploration of the telephone network, began gaining momentum in the 1950s (Borders, 2009). Social media evolved and can be depicted in many forms. Among the most popular of their forms, were Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube, with different platforms of social networking formula to accumulate users. Twitter, which is now X, for example, is considered to be the world’s real-time newspaper (O’Reilly & Milstein, 2009) because it is a microblogging website (Kelsey, 2010) wherein messages sent and received are not over 280, which started with 140 characters, or just about how long a news headline is (O’Reilly & Milstein, 2009). Facebook, on the other hand, which seems to have copied Friendster’s initial design as a dating and social introduction service (Menn. In Kiehne, 2004), has a platform that allows account holders to post updates with much longer length compared to Twitter, share photos and videos of events, and the like.

Among their primary uses, social media tools like e-mail and online social networks such as Facebook and MySpace got their kick-off to connecting millions of people. They restructured online neighborhoods (Kanter & Fine, 2010). Social media

use is becoming more widespread in communication, educational, business, and even personal spheres due to its capacity to allow users to connect, interact, and share. Through social networking, people can revive old friendships and connect with old classmates and coworkers. (White, King, & Tsang (Eds.), 2011).

Social media eventually became a buzzword that even any field of research seems to attach them all the time. They are specifically a topic of any discourse vis-à-vis behavioral matters. While many areas of behavioral addiction cause a debate about whether some excessive behaviors should even be taken into consideration as real addictions (e.g., internet use, sex, exercise, video game playing, among others), a similar debate holds true for social networking mania (Griffiths, 2013).

Also, social media for education and communication have eventually transformed to be widespread, dynamic, distributed, timely, team-based, bottom-up, many-to-many, value-based, and individualized (White et al. (Eds.), 2011). Thus, making it a very effective tool for communicative processes among teachers and students. Some call this enterprise Education 2.0, but it must be made understood to be an early futuristic view of the whole educational process (White et al. (Eds.), 2011). This can be dubbed, therefore, as Communication 2.0 (White et al. (Eds.), 2011).

Hyper-connected life has been re-imagined for the digital age brought about by this information society. Rajesh and Michael (2015) showed how social media became a buzzword.

Indeed, social media has become part of everyone's life. There is no stopping the proliferation of social networking sites as they continue to reach a large number of people called netizens daily. There are always two sides regarding their effects on people's lives – a boon and a bane. Rajesh and Michael (2015) proved social media's effectiveness in education and communication. As they said, 89 percent of the people

with an 18-29 age limit is by any means connected to social media. The students use social media occasionally for educational and communicative purposes.

It is clear that individuals are more willing to use social media in their personal lives than to use it for professional or other purposes. (Seaman & Tinti-Kane, 2013). According to Seaman and Tinti-Kane (2013), the personal use of social media among individuals reflected that of the general population. They further said that the use of social media has lagged somewhat behind their personal use but has increased each year. Recently, a great number of individuals utilized social media in a professional context, which is any aspect of their profession outside of their main jobs (Seaman & Tinti-Kane, 2013). As a rule, they saw considerable potential in applying social media and technology to their jobs, but only with several serious barriers.

Social Media on Education

This research is not focused on education; however, it might also be good to note some educational points of view regarding communicative processes. Goldfarb et al. (2011) stated that educational networking through proper communication channeling has the potential to improve student learning. They said that studies examining blogging, micro-blogging (e.g., Twitter), and wiki initiatives indicated that social networking enriched the learning environment in the following ways: early recognition of student needs and formative assessment, establishment of classroom community, student engagement, increased sense of student achievement, information management, and access to marginalized students, which are attributed to the communicative aspect of social media.

The shift in focus of web applications towards social collaboration, networking, and interaction has occurred in recent years. One thing to take into consideration is

the rising importance of social media, which encompasses various applications for the publication of user-generated content (Safran, 2010). He emphasized that social media has also influenced technology-enhanced learning and teaching, and the collaborative aspects of social media align with constructivist learning theory, while the communicative aspects can be applied to promote informal learning.

Various studies have emerged, especially on the utilization of social media with informatization. Modern society has been affected by social media and has changed some of people's habits (Tiryakioglu & Erzurum, 2011). Effective utilization of features and opportunities of social networks engendered instructors' empowering of education through the communicative process with active learning, creativity, problem-solving, cooperation, and multifaceted interactions as well as students' utility and improvement of their academic performance, inquiry, and alternative thinking skills.

Raut and Patil (2016) affirmed that the use of social media has been swiftly increasing during the last few years. Moreover, they said that it is not only being used by working people, but also there was a heavy rise in the use of social media by students or in education, most specifically for communicative processes.

Brady, Holcomb, and Smith (2010), on the other hand, found that distance education as a primary means of instruction is expanding significantly at the college and university levels.

They said that the simultaneous growth of SNS, including Facebook, LinkedIn, and MySpace among today's college students, must have caused the increasing number of higher education instructors who are beginning to combine distance education delivery with SNSs' powerful tools for communication.

Combining traditional classroom teaching with online teaching through SNS communication tools such as Facebook, WhatsApp, and many others is booming. For

example, since Malaysians spend most of their time outside of class online with a clear preference for entertainment and social media, it is believed that using an online tool to supplement teaching the upper class will be in line with current trends (Manan et al., 2012) and that it would be very beneficial, particularly for the learners.

According to Miller, Schweingruber, and Brandenburg (2000), the greater the prevalence of computer technology in the daily lives of middle school students, the wider the impact on their learning environment. They found that students of both genders and different levels of socio-economic status were well on their way to becoming part of the digital culture. Describing the benefits of this technological tool and analyzing the potential pitfalls and challenges it could create, Espino (2015) said there were specific ways in which EFL or English as a Foreign Language instructors use Facebook not only as a teaching tool but also as a very effective communication platform. Aside from Facebook, the most popular tools were Wiki, YouTube, bulletin board, LinkedIn, blogging, and twitting. Social media tools have become ubiquitous, and students used them all the time for communication, even inside the classroom. Liu's (2010) study revealed that the top three used social media tools were YouTube, Facebook, and Wikipedia. The top four reasons for social media tools usage were direction communication, social engagement, speed of feedback, and relationship building. When it comes to social media groups, she said, students prefer a civically engaged group that does not require membership, and a group based on contemporary themes may not last long. She also suggested some educational implications of these instruments as a valuable resource for teaching and learning.

Social media tools are rapidly changing the landscape of communications, and their emergence has significantly impacted how instructors teach and students learn (Griesemer, 2014). In today's higher education environment, instructors, students, and

others all together collaborate on the tasks of knowledge construction. Klopfer et al. (2009) believed that technology can have a reciprocal relationship with teaching so that the emergence of new technologies challenges educators to not only understand but also leverage these technologies for classroom utilization; at the same time, the classroom implementation of these technologies can have a direct impact on how these technologies continue to take shape.

Usluel and Mazman (2009) explained the possibility of Web 2.0 tools utilization for education, such as social networks, podcasts, blogs, and wikis, from the point of the importance of interaction for distance education and investigated its adoption process in distance education by giving definitions to theories and models which have variegated constructs that affect this process. Web 2.0 technologies, including (SNSs) like MySpace and Facebook, and content-sharing sites such as YouTube and Flickr, allowed members to establish or maintain connections with others, articulate their social networks, and present themselves. SNSs are among the most visited sites on the internet today (McCarthy, 2009).

Social media is currently being utilized regularly by millions of people, and its uses have been widespread (Prakash & Pankaj, 2015). Indeed, it has caught the attention of both academic and industry researchers worldwide mainly because it has become a powerful tool for communication.

There is an ongoing debate regarding the usage of social media at work and, specifically, the integration of it in education through various communicative processes. Social media usage advocates mentioned the benefits of using social media for academic practice and communication. At the same time, critics called for not only regulations but also the removal of such online technologies in the classroom.

As an educational and communicative tool, social media enhances the learning experience by giving students and teachers a venue to interact and connect in new, exciting ways. Web sites like Facebook, X, formerly Twitter, and LinkedIn provided an avenue where users can find answers to questions, dialog, and exchange ideas. These sites are designed to foster discussion as well as collaboration.

The accruing availability of technology-driven learning tools in education and communication has pushed scholars to explore ways in which learning could be enhanced through emerging technologies (Absalom & de Saint Léger, 2011). According to Joyce (2013), this trend has been given stronger impetus with the emergence of Web 2.0 technologies and the proliferation of social networking practices such as Facebook, MySpace, YouTube, and blogs, to name but a few. According to Luqman et al. (2012) the 21st century is a period of uncertainty, chaos, and complexities, making it a major challenge to educational institutions. Luqman et al. (2012) further emphasized that it is imperative to keep users up to date with the changing technology and point out that institutions lagging in the technological sector cannot face the pace of the world.

Lederer (2012) discussed the pros and cons of social media in the classroom. She said its potential as an educational and communicative tool can enhance student engagement and improve communications among students and teachers. It can also prepare students for future employment. Despite these benefits, critics argued that there were serious risks to usage of social media in the classroom. They contended that social media can be a distraction, trigger cyberbullying, and discourage face-to-face communication. Waycott et al. (2009) mentioned the foregoing usability issues, stating that students and staff shared concerns about replacing face-to-face interactions and communication issues.

Kaplan's (2003) study indicated that psychosocial health predicted preference levels for social interaction online, which, in turn, predicted negative results related to problematic internet use. In addition, the results of his study indicated that the influence of psychosocial distress on adverse outcomes due to internet use was mediated by online socialization preference and other symptoms of problematic internet use. Also, the results espoused that that individuals' preference for online, rather than face-to-face, social interaction had an importance in the development of negative consequences associated with problematic internet use.

However, Al-Aufi and Fulton's (2014) findings showed a progressive social networking tools usage for informal scholarly communication. They stated that there was perceived usefulness of the social networking tools' impact on patterns of informal scholarly communication, and empirical findings provided a broad understanding regarding the potential of social networking tools on informal scholarly communication in areas of humanities and social sciences disciplines.

It is reasonable to note what Turkle (2004) emphasized. He posited that the methods of thought employed were influenced by the tools utilized. The development of written language resulted in a fundamental change in the way people organize, process, transmit, and preserve world representations. Even if writing is still the primary form of information technology, people tend to focus on computers when they consider how technology has changed their mental patterns.

The growing interest in social media has led many individuals to examine its use for academic and communicative practices, thereby challenging institutions of higher learning to enhance collaborative learning and community building among students. Indeed, social media holds promise for academia. It must also be noted that

students have diverse experiences, perceptions, and beliefs with regard to social media technologies.

According to Minocha (2009), the growing interest in social dimensions of learning has led institutions to adopt virtual learning environments (VLEs), which incorporated communication and collaboration tools such as blogs, wikis, chats, and forums. She mentioned that online interactions, such as discussions or collaborations using forums, wikis, or blogs, enabled knowledge to be constructed individually but mediated socially (Anderson, 2008).

Deng and Yuen (2010) revealed that in the past decade, personal homepages, as the dominant self-publishing vehicle on the internet, have been replaced by blogs (Wortham, 2007). According to a recent report by Technorati, the leading blog search engine, 133M blog records were created since 2002, with approximately 900,000 blog posts in 24 hours (Technorati, 2008). The explosive growth of blogs can be attributed to their ease of use, flexibility, and interactivity. Some reasons can also be considered. First, blogging technology is lightweight, easy to use, and cost-efficient (Blood, 2004). It significantly lowered the technical threshold of publishing online by allowing people with little or no programming skills to create online content. Second, as a flexible, versatile, and fluid medium (Herring et al., 2005), blogs can be redesigned for a wide variety of needs or purposes ranging from the casual release of emotions to task-oriented group collaboration (Nardi et al., 2004). Third, the interactive functionalities of hyperlinking and commenting allow for social connections and interaction between the bloggers and their audience. Therefore, the combination of a myriad of user-generated content, the user-friendly interface, and the possibilities of social connections and interaction contributed to the popularity of blogs (Du & Wagner, 2006).

Interest in social media was also coupled with changes in everyone's likings. For instance, since 2006, blogging has decreased among young adults and teens while rising among older adults. As the technology and tools embedded in social networking sites evolved and the use of the sites continued to grow, the youth may be exchanging 'macro-blogging' for microblogging with status updates (Lenhart et al., 2010).

In the automobile training industry where this research was conducted, trainees considered Facebook as old-fashioned. Most of them no longer hold Facebook accounts; instead, they have Instagram, Snapchat, and other newer social media which has microblogging features. Indeed, blogging has declined in popularity not only among teens but also young adults since 2006. According to Lenhart et al. (2010), even blog commenting has also dropped among teens.

In recent years, there has been a rapid increase in social networking tools usage of Facebook and social media in general, mainly for the purposes of socialization, recreation, and entertainment (Smith et al., 2009). Many educators thought that these tools gave new educational affordances and avenues for learners to interact not only with one another but with their teachers or tutors as well (Poellhuber & Anderson, 2011). Furthermore, these tools may be of particular interest to distance education institutions because of their potential to contribute to the essential social integration associated with persistence (Sweet, 1986; Tinto, 1975) due to the traditional problem of documented dropout rates in distance courses. (Rovai, 2003; Woodley, 2004). However, because distance students are often older than regular mainstream students (Bean & Metzner, 1985; Rovai, 2003), not much is disclosed about their expertise with social media or their interests in taking advantage of these tools for informal learning or collaborating with classmates.

Also, Chen and Bryer, (2012) agreed that the use of social media has surged globally in recent years, saying that based on individual companies' statistics in July 2011, Facebook passed 750M users; LinkedIn had over 100M members; Twitter hit over 177M tweets per day; YouTube reached 3B views every day. They also stated that social media is infiltrating the educational arena, and online social networks were increasingly being utilized not only by instructors, but also by college students for several reasons (Mazer et al., 2007; 2009). Therefore, understanding how individuals behave on such websites is a potentially valuable source of information for both researchers and educators.

Social media has become an integral part of modern-day communication, with vast implications for social relationships, including those between teachers and students. Several scholars have studied the relationship between social media culture between teachers and students. Indeed, social media platforms have become an integral part of everyday life for many people, and their use is increasingly common in various areas of society, including education. In recent years, several studies have been conducted for the investigation of the means in which social media can be used for teacher-learner communication. It is suggested that social media can offer benefits such as increased engagement, improved communication, and supportive learning communities (Beneito-Montagut, 2017; Gao et al., 2012; Junco, 2015). However, concerns about the privacy and safety of learners have been raised (Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010). Social media platforms may pose privacy and security concerns, particularly when sharing personal information (Boyd & Ellison, 2008).

Studies have found that social media can facilitate communication between teachers and learners and can have a positive impact on learning outcomes. Beneito-Montagut (2017) highlighted the potential positive outcomes of social media

communication in the learner-teacher relationship, including increased trust, communication, and collaboration. Furthermore, social media can enable learners to connect with peer learners outside of the classroom (Beneito-Montagut, 2017). Engaging in social communication allows learners to feel more connected to their peers and contributes to the development of supportive learning communities (Gao et al., 2021).

The use of social media for communication between teachers and learners can also enhance engagement and learning outcomes. By using social media, learning becomes a more interactive and collaborative experience (Gao et al., 2021; Junco, 2015). Studies have also shown the potential for social media to provide learners with access to a plethora of resources and information that can aid their learning (Beneito-Montagut, 2017; Gao et al., 2021). Additionally, social media use can contribute to the development of critical thinking skills (Beneito-Montagut, 2017). However, the use of social media in education may lead to information overload, particularly when it comes to the sharing of resources and information (Rosen, 2011), and may be a distraction for learners, particularly when it comes to the use of social media for non-educational purposes (Junco, 2015).

Despite the potential benefits of social media utilization, there are also risks and challenges that should be considered. Privacy and safety concerns are among the most significant issues associated with social media use in education (Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010). Social media can expose learners to risks such as cyberbullying, harassment, and threats. Learners may also be vulnerable to unintended consequences, such as oversharing or posting personal information on social media platforms (Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010).

Moreover, social media use can lead to distractions and reduced attention spans, which may negatively impact learners' academic performance, particularly in terms of reading, writing, and critical thinking (Rosen et al., 2011). Social media integration into learning activities should be carefully designed and managed to promote desirable results and reduce the risks of negative consequences.

Gao et al. (2021) suggested that the integration of social media into learning environments should be focused on enhancing communication skills rather than solely on technology. Teachers should take on the role of facilitator rather than knowledge provider, creating opportunities for learners to engage in discussions and collaborations.

Similarly, Beneito-Montagut (2017) suggested that social media use should be integrated into a more significant pedagogical strategy aimed at enhancing interactions, contributing to the development of critical thinking, and promoting active learning. Teachers should focus on creating a sense of community among learners and between the teacher and learners (Beneito-Montagut, 2017).

Other best practices include providing learners with clear guidelines and expectations for social media use, establishing rules for appropriate behavior, and providing training on how to use various social media platforms (Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010). Teachers should also be aware of privacy issues and should take appropriate measures to ensure that learners' personal information is protected (Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010).

According to a study by Junco (2015), social media has revolutionized interpersonal communication among teachers and students. The study contended that social media platforms provided a new way to communicate with students. Social media platforms can be utilized by teachers to share classroom experiences,

participate in professional development communities, and develop student relationships. However, the study noted that social media interactions between teachers and students should maintain proper boundaries.

Another study by Pattanapichet and Wichadee (2015) found that social media usage by teachers can help students develop critical thinking skills. The study analyzed the impact of social media on students' attitudes towards learning and found that students who engaged with teachers on social media platforms had a better attitude towards learning. However, the study emphasizes the importance of ensuring that social media interactions between teachers and students maintain proper boundaries.

The study by Manca and Ranieri (2016) focused on the impact of social media on students' academic and psychosocial development. The study found that social media usage among teachers and students established a collaborative learning environment that fostered academic and psychosocial development. Social media usage also created a sense of community among students. However, the study notes that social media risks, such as cyberbullying and privacy issues, must be addressed to maintain safe social media interactions.

Harbaugh et al. (2015) focused on how teacher usage of social media has the potential to improve the attitudes and behavior of learners towards learning. The study demonstrates that social media can provide learners a platform for connecting and interacting with their teachers, leading to increased engagement and interest in learning.

Duncan et al. (2017) provided empirical evidence that the use of social media provides learners with a space where they can engage with teachers and other learners, sharing ideas and perspectives in an open forum. The study concludes that

social media can provide the means for establishing a dynamic learning environment that fosters collaboration and active engagement.

Finally, a study by Ford, Bowden, and Beard (2011) examined the use of social media for teacher-student collaborations. The study found that social media platforms brought teacher-student relationships into a public space that fosters collaborative learning. Social media also created a dynamic learning environment where teachers and students could share, discuss, and exchange ideas. The study concludes that social media possesses the potential to transform traditional teacher-student relationships and foster collaborations that could lead to better academic outcomes.

However, it is important to acknowledge potential risks as well. While social media can provide a platform for engagement between teachers and learners, concerns have been raised about the potential for cyberbullying and inappropriate behavior. It is critical that ethical concerns are considered when implementing social media use in educational settings and appropriate measures put in place to safeguard students' well-being.

Overall, social media has significant potential to enhance communication between teachers and learners, creating a more collaborative and dynamic learning environment. It is important to deliberate and consider student safety and the appropriate use of social media in educational settings.

In general, social media has changed the way teachers and students interact. The reviewed literature indicates that social media platforms provide several benefits for students, including academic and psychosocial development. However, proper boundaries and safeguards must be established to protect students from online risks.

Social Media on Organizational Culture

On the other hand, Blau and McKinley (2018) explored the impact of social media on organizational culture. They argued that social media platforms transformed how organizations communicated and interacted with their employees. They discussed how social media could either reinforce existing organizational culture or facilitate the emergence of a new culture.

Additionally, Kietzmann et al. (2011) provided a comprehensive framework for understanding the functional building blocks of social media. They argued that social media platforms enable organizations to foster community, engage in dialogue, facilitate collaboration, and build relationships. Social media functions can significantly impact an organization's culture and communication dynamics.

Also, Lee, Sung, and Choi (2017) investigated the effects of social media use on employees' attitudes toward organizational change. They found that social media platforms could be practical tools for facilitating employee participation and engagement in organizational change processes. The study suggested that social media could influence an organization's culture by shaping employees' attitudes and behaviors.

Wiesenfeld, Raghuram, and Garud (2013) explored the role of organizational culture in the failure of digitalization efforts in the newspaper industry. The authors argued that the existing organizational culture, which was resistant to change and technological advancements, hindered the successful adoption of social media and digital platforms. This study highlighted the importance of aligning organizational culture with social media strategies.

Waters et al. (2009) examined how nonprofit organizations utilize social media, specifically Facebook, to engage stakeholders. The study revealed that social media

platforms could facilitate the creation of online communities and foster relationships between organizations and their stakeholders. These findings suggested that social media can shape an organization's culture by enabling more open and transparent communication with stakeholders.

Indeed, social media platforms have become a ubiquitous part of our lives, and their use in education as well as in organizations is growing. While there are potential benefits of social media use in enhancing communication between teachers and learners and between workers in organizations, it is essential to consider the risks and challenges of these platforms. Careful planning and management are required to reduce the risks associated with social media use in education and organizations. Best practices suggest creating a community, establishing behavior guidelines, and safeguarding student privacy. The use of social media in education and organizations can promote communication skills, improve learning outcomes and productivity, and contribute to the development of critical thinking.

Little study has been done, especially on the connection between associates' and trainees' use of social media and their productivity at work. However, certain pertinent research emphasizes the significance of social media use and its influence on workers' general performance and behavior.

According to one pertinent study by Neubaum, Pagán, and Garcia (2014), who looked at the impacts of social media use on employee productivity, using social media excessively at work can harm productivity. This study stresses the necessity for additional research into the precise effects of associate and trainee social media culture on their performance at work.

Mesch, Talmud, and Quan-Haase (2012) investigated the connection between employees' use of social media and their job happiness in a different study. The results

showed that workers who used social media for professional purposes had greater job satisfaction. The lack of a particular focus on the social media usage culture among associates and trainees in this study emphasizes the need for more research.

Overall, the body of extant research offers scant insights into how associates' and trainees' use of social media affects their productivity at work. In order to comprehend the precise dynamics and effects of social media culture on these people's performance, a research gap must be filled.

Chapter III

FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

Computer-mediated communication (CMC) (Walther, 2011) served as the anchor of this study. This theory served as the theoretical framework for studying how social media culture among associates and trainees affected their performance in the workplace. CMC refers to the interaction between individuals through digital platforms, such as social media, instant messaging, and video conferencing, which have become increasingly prevalent in work settings (Walther, 2011). It explored how communication and interaction between individuals are facilitated through various platforms. In the context of social media culture and its impact on associates' and trainees' performance in the workplace, the CMC framework helped to understand the underlying mechanisms and dynamics at play.

This study aimed to analyze how the social media culture among associates and trainees influenced their performance in the workplace. The CMC framework was utilized, providing a comprehensive understanding of computer-mediated communication's effects on individual's behaviors, attitudes, and outcomes.

On the other hand, it assumed that associates and trainees engaged in a shared social media culture within the workplace. This culture included the use of social media platforms for communication, collaboration, and information sharing among colleagues. On the other hand, it was assumed that performance in the workplace was influenced by various factors, including the social media culture among associates and trainees. It suggested that the nature of their social media interactions could impact their productivity, satisfaction, and overall job performance.

The study focused on the impact of social media culture on associates and trainees within the workplace. It considered the influence of social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn and internal communication tools like Slack or Microsoft Teams. The study context was primarily within organizational settings, where associates and trainees engaged with each other and their superiors through *computer-mediated communication* (Walther, 2011).

The theoretical framework of CMC originated from the broader field of communication studies, particularly the study of mediated communication. Scholars, such as Joseph Walther, have extensively researched the effects of CMC on interpersonal communication, group dynamics, and social relationships (Walther, 2011). The framework had been applied to various domains, including education, healthcare, and business, to examine the impacts of digital communication on performance and outcomes.

Walther (2011) argued that *computer-mediated communication* encompassed various digital platforms for interaction, such as social media, instant messaging, and video conferencing. The study employed the theoretical framework of *computer-mediated communication* (CMC) to explore the impact of social media culture on workplace performance (Walther, 2011).

Looking into the CMC, the independent variable - social media culture, mediating variable – participation, and the dependent variable - performance were considered. To illustrate the relationship between the independent variable, social media culture, and the dependent variable, performance, a quantitative research design was used, such as a survey or an experiment. The level of participation in social media was measured using various indicators, such as frequency of posting,

commenting, liking, sharing, or the amount of time spent on social media platforms like what Kwak et al. (2010) and Verduyn et al. (2015) had done.

For example, in the survey, participants were asked to indicate how often they engage in different activities on social media, such as sharing updates with colleagues, corresponding with one another regarding shared information, or sharing valuable information. Each activity was assigned a numerical value, and the overall level of participation was calculated by summing up these values.

On the other hand, measuring the independent variable, social media culture, was more complex, as it involved capturing the broader cultural norms, values, and practices related to social media. Social media culture was also analyzed through cultural studies lens. Cultural studies scholars analyzed it by investigating the ways in which power dynamics and cultural processes influence the production and consumption of content on social media platforms. They explored how social media platforms were embedded within broader social, political, economic contexts, and how they reflected and reinforced existing power structures and ideologies. One influential figure in cultural studies is Stuart Hall. His work on cultural studies has had a significant impact on the analysis of social media culture. His concept of encoding or decoding provided a framework for understanding how meaning was constructed, negotiated, and interpreted within cultural contexts. In the context of social media culture, this concept could be applied to explore how users encode and decode messages and how different interpretations and readings of content could emerge.

By applying cultural studies lens, insights into the complex interplay between culture, power, and social media could be gained. This lens allowed for critical examination of social media platforms as sites where cultural meanings were

produced, contested, and negotiated, and where power relations were both reproduced and challenged. Indicators to measure social media culture included:

First was perceived social norms. Participants were asked to rate their agreement with statements reflecting social norms on social media, such as which social media platforms were commonly used within their multicultural organization, or the frequency of social media platforms use for communication and collaboration within their multicultural organization.

Second was engagement with other social media users within the organization. For instance, participants were asked about how frequently they actively participated in discussions or conversations on social media platforms.

Third was the possible list of reasons why social media culture was created. Participants were asked about the main motivation behind its emergence as well as its impact on traditional forms of communication.

Fourth was performance in the workplace. For example, participants were asked about their ability to manage time effectively, prioritize tasks, balance social media use with work responsibility, among others.

Fifth was the added value social media culture to organization communication. Participants were asked about how much value the created social media culture added to organizational communication, to what extent it improved the speed and efficiency of communication within the organization, and how they rated the effectiveness of the created social media culture in promoting collaboration and teamwork among themselves.

These indicators were measured using Likert scale items or multiple-choice questions in the survey and through qualitative methods such as interviews or focus

groups to gather in-depth insights into participants' perceptions and experiences of social media culture.

By utilizing the CMC framework, the study provided a comprehensive understanding of how social media culture influences associates' and trainees' performance in the workplace. The framework helped to analyze the underlying mechanisms and effects of *computer-mediated communication*, particularly in relation to social influence, social learning, social identity, and social presence. This enabled the exploration and explanation of the complex relationships between social media culture and workplace outcomes to a deeper understanding of the phenomenon.

Conceptual Framework

Social media has become integral to people's lives, influencing how individuals interact, share information, and engage with others. This conceptual framework explored the relationship between social media culture as the independent variable and performance as the dependent variable within the context of online platforms. By

understanding the dynamics of participation and its impact on social media culture, insights were gained into the evolving nature of online social interactions.

Independent Variable: Social Media Culture

Social media culture encompasses the shared norms, values, and practices that emerge within the social media environment. It reflects how individuals perceive and engage with the online social world. This includes aspects such as perceived social norms, engagement with social media influencers, self-presentation, and social comparison (Kwak et al., 2010; Verduyn et al., 2015). Social media culture shapes the way individuals interact, express themselves, and establish connections in the digital realm.

Mediating Variable: Participation

Participation in social media refers to individuals' engagement and activities on various online platforms. It involves actions such as posting updates, commenting on others' posts, sharing content, and liking posts (Kwak et al., 2010; Verduyn et al., 2015). These activities reflect the level and frequency of engagement with social media platforms and form the foundation of an individual's digital presence.

Dependent Variable: Performance

Performance indicates the outcomes or results of user's participation within the given social media culture. Performance was measured within the context and objectives of the study. It included metrics such as reach, engagement, user satisfaction, brand loyalty, conversion rates, and other relevant indicators that

assessed users' activities' effectiveness, efficiency, or success within the social media platform.

Overall, this conceptual framework suggests that social media culture influences users' participation, and in turn, users' participation influences their performance outcomes within the social media environment. The framework provides a structure for exploring and understanding the relationships among these variables and their impact on individuals or organizations operating within the realm of social media.

Operational Definition of Terms

Reasons for Social Media Culture Creation The underlying factors or motivations that contribute to the formation and development of social media culture. It includes reasons such as the need for self-expression, desire for social connection, information sharing, entertainment, personal branding, and seeking validation or recognition within the online community.

Norms and Practices of Social Media Users The observed patterns of behavior, practices, and unwritten rules followed by social media users within the cultural context of specific platform. It encompasses practices like content creation sharing, commenting, liking, following, engaging

with other users, adhering to community guidelines, etiquette, and expectations of authenticity or self-presentation.

Usual Media Users' Engagement

The degree to which social media users actively participate, interact, and contribute within social media culture. It includes indicators such as frequency of posting, commenting, sharing, liking, interacting with the users' content, joining or creating communities, participating in challenges or trends, and overall involvement in community activities.

Social Media Culture Value Added

The benefits, advantages, or positive impacts that social media culture brings to the realm of organizational communication. It encompasses aspects such as improved brand visibility, users' engagement, targeted marketing, real-time feedback, users' collaboration, employee advocacy, knowledge sharing, networking opportunities, and fostering a sense of community among stakeholders.

Chapter IV

METHODOLOGY

This one-shot survey research design with qualitative methods for triangulation was in the inclination to learn the correlation between social media culture among associates and trainees and their performance in the workplace. It specifically investigated how social media culture was created in a multicultural organization, how the online members' participation translated into action, why this emerging culture was created, and what value added it had on organizational communication.

Research Design

This research initially utilized a one-shot survey, with the employment of qualitative methods eventually for triangulation of data drawn to provide a comprehensive understanding of social media culture in a multicultural organization.

There were 234 respondents who answered the questionnaire. They comprised both the associates, who were mostly instructors and trainees at an automobile training industry in Jeddah, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. They were given the questionnaire to accomplish a maximum of one day on different and convenient schedules. One period of the trainees' class was allotted to this, and the respective subject instructors administered it simultaneously. On the other hand, the instructors completed the questionnaire on the given survey day in accordance with their availability. Originally, the plan was for questionnaire sheets to be personally handed to these participants. However, the pandemic hindered the execution. As a countermeasure, the researcher uploaded the research questionnaire via Microsoft Forms, which took about a week to accomplish. Not to mention, the translation

odyssey prolonged the process. Google translator was used, and all translation was verified by an English Instructor who is a Saudi National. The administration of the survey was completely done online for this matter. Nevertheless, the focus group discussion among the selected 8 instructors was conducted face-to-face following the minimum requirement for safety during the crisis. Also, data collection involved an in-depth interview with the five of the key stakeholders in the organization, including managers and associates from other departments. The interviews were conducted either in person or online, depending on the location and availability of the participants. The interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed for analysis. Overall, it was difficult to go through the pertinent procedures, but the gathering of data was finally achieved.

By gathering qualitative data through focus group discussions and interviews, a deeper understanding on the association between social media culture and performance were gained. Both allowed the exploration on how associates and trainees use social media in their daily lives, including their motivations, patterns of usage, and preferred platforms. Participants shared their experiences, routines, and the types of content they engaged with on social media. These insights helped in understanding the specific social media practices of the target population. Also, through them deeper investigation of the impact of social media use on workplace performance were possible. Participants discussed how social media affects their productivity, concentration, and time management at work. They shared examples of how social media distractions or excessive use have influenced their work tasks or interactions with colleagues. These narratives provided qualitative evidence of the potential challenges and benefits associated with social media use in the workplace. Additionally, they enabled the examination of participants' attitudes and perceptions

toward social media use in a professional context. Participants shared their opinions on topics such as the appropriateness of social media use during work hours, the impact of social media on their professional image or reputation, and their awareness of organizational social media policies. These insights shed light on the participants' views and beliefs, which helped in understanding the underlying factors that shape their behaviors. Moreover, they assessed the social media skills and knowledge of associates and trainees. Participants were inquired about their familiarity with various social media platforms, their understanding of privacy settings, and their ability to distinguish between personal and professional use of social media. These discussions provided qualitative data on participants' digital literacy and competence in navigating social media platforms, which contributed to the understanding of their performance in the workplace. Lastly, through them best practices and strategies for managing social media use effectively in the workplace were discovered. Participants shared techniques they employed to maintain a balance between work responsibilities and social media engagement, examples of how they utilize social media for professional networking or knowledge sharing, or insights into how they mitigate distractions caused by social media. These insights could be valuable for organizations seeking to establish guidelines or training programs related to social media use in the workplace.

Lastly, the data were analyzed by viewing summaries of each survey question. After viewing the overall question summaries, rules to answer more specific questions about the collected data were created. For instance, compare rules were employed to cross-tabulate the data to compare the answer choices to one question across the rest of the survey.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Jeddah, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia at an automobile training industry, a non-profit institute where Japanese Automobile Distributors in the Kingdom (JADIK) shared construction cost with Japan Automobile Manufacturers Association Inc. (JAMA), and both the Saudi Arabian and Japanese governments supported in providing land tools, equipment, and experts. The institute was founded in 2003. It provides job-oriented technical training for young Saudi high school graduates who have the passion for automobile and maintenance field for Japanese cars. It has supervision, support, and patronage of the Japanese Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry (METI), JAMA, and JADIK.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents were associates and trainees at an automobile training industry. The associates consisted of expatriates from the Philippines, Indonesia, Pakistan, India, and Sri-Lanka, and the trainees all comprised Saudi nationals. There were 32 associates and 202 trainees as respondents covered. Both were drawn from among the total number of regular associates and trainees in this multicultural organization.

Sampling Techniques

Cochran's formula with a confidence level of 95%, confidence interval of 5, and a total number of 35 instructors and 423 trainees, the study arrived at a sample size of 234.

The following formula to get the sample size was used:

$$\text{Actual sample size} = \frac{n \times N}{n + (N - 1)}$$

Where:

n = total number of population of a given group

N = the overall population at study

Calculating the actual sample size for:

423 Trainees

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Actual sample size} &= \frac{n \times N}{n + (N - 1)} \\ &= \frac{384 \times 423}{384 + (423 - 1)} \\ &= \frac{162,432}{384 + 422} \\ &= \frac{162,432}{806} \\ &= 202 \end{aligned}$$

So, the actual number of trainees selected as samples was 202.

35 Associates

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Actual sample size} &= \frac{n \times N}{n + (N - 1)} \\ &= \frac{384 \times 35}{384 + (35 - 1)} \\ &= \frac{13,440}{384 + 34} \\ &= \frac{13,440}{418} \\ &= 32 \end{aligned}$$

So, the actual number of associates selected as samples was 32.

Research Instrument

The survey was based on appropriate questions carefully formulated. It initially consisted of about 45 questions which were all in relation to correlation between social media culture among associates and trainees and their performance in the workplace. More questions were added eventually along the way. The main instrument used was a survey questionnaire wherein most parts were translated in Arabic. It comprised of different parts including the demographic profiling in the first part excluded in the initial 45 questions. The rest of the parts answered how social media culture was created in a multicultural organization, clarified how social media culture in an organization affected performance, demonstrated how the online members' participation translated into action, enumerated the reasons why this emerging culture was created and exposed what value added it had on organizational communication.

Instrument Validation

To validate the questionnaire used in this study, three experts in the field of communication looked into it; then pilot testing was conducted. There was a little revision done. Cronbach's Alpha was used for reliability test. To make sure the results were valid, the same statistician was consulted all throughout the segments where statistician was needed.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data for this research was collected using a survey questionnaire. The survey was based on appropriate questions carefully formulated. It initially consisted of about 45 questions which were all in relation to social media culture among associates and trainees and their performance in the workplace. The Likert scale was

used to gauge respondents' responses in some statements. Chi square and phi coefficient were also used for cross tabulation references.

Focus Group Discussion was employed for triangulation of measure to further explain the results.

After the constituted DComm Advisory Committee's approval, validated questionnaire sheets were distributed via Microsoft Forms in a nonprofit institute in Jeddah, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia mentioned in the research locale of this study.

The confidentiality of the answered survey sheets was assured since the identities of the respondents were not necessary to be revealed. The participants were afforded the option to remain anonymous given the fact that their conscience might affect their honesty and effectiveness in answering each item in the survey and reasonable time to answer the survey.

It was made absolutely understood that there were completely no monetary incentives offered for their participation. However, refreshments were served during the conduct of the focus group discussion. A treat to dinner in a restaurant was arranged for those who lent a hand especially in uploading the questionnaire in Microsoft Forms, administering the survey online, collating the data, among others.

Questions were planned and prepared for personal interview with some of the respondents. A few front-liner in the field of teaching like the English and Technical instructors in the institute as well as the JADIK trainees were closely interviewed.

Data Analysis

The first statistical task was to do a descriptive analysis of variables. The results obtained for each type of variable were presented. For qualitative and dichotomous

variables, results were presented as frequencies and percentages. For quantitative variables, the presentation was as means and deviations. After this analysis, the association between variables, and predictive analysis based on chi square and phi coefficient was assessed through series of cross tabulations.

The distributions of age, gender, race/ethnicity, religious beliefs, and any measures of socio-economic status such as income, education level, and access to internet had been looked into. These distributions helped to inform the analysis in terms of possible age-adjustment, weighting, and other analytical tools available to address issues of bias and non-representative samples.

Chapter V

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Drawn from among the total number of regular associates and trainees at an automobile training industry as shown in Figure 1, the first set of respondents was the 32 associates mostly instructors consisting of expatriates from the Philippines (10), Indonesia (7), Pakistan (6), India (5), and Sri-Lanka (1), and Saudi nationals (3). The second set of respondents was the 202 trainees who signed contract for Toyota, Honda, Mazda, Mitsubishi, Isuzu, Suzuki and Nissan automotive workshops in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The trainees are all Saudi nationals.

Indeed, this research proved that variegated platforms for communication have created an environment rather easier than ever for individuals of diverse backgrounds to link one another.

Diversity and inclusion initiatives by this automobile training industry underpin the realization that everybody is distinct from one another. Social media underprops the foregoing truth, bespeaking that instructors and trainees altogether are more linked and have more in common with one another when they engage in any correspondence utilizing different platforms. It is considered their opportunity to connect with colleagues of all different backgrounds for the purpose of sharing experiences, finding commonalities, and overcoming challenges in contemporary means. In any social media tenets, it can be achieved through sharing their own experience of an activity that is happening, a photo that induces various feedback, or even a simple hashtag that incites a plethora of opinions and ideas. The instructors and the trainees commonly use YouTube, WhatsApp, Snapchat, and Instagram. Strangely, the most popular social networking,

Facebook seems to be not so much of their option given only 72 out of 234 are Facebook users shown in Figure 1.

Thanks to the smartphone revolution, most individuals now carry a sophisticated computer in their pockets. As the first generation to grow up surrounded by technology, millennials are often seen as having embraced it. Outside experiences that were previously difficult to obtain in the same way are now more readily available.

Different types of communication have been made possible by social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, and others. One can communicate with new people through email, text messaging, Facebook Messenger, tweets, Instagram tagging, FaceTime, and other channels rather than just a phone conversation. Devices used for correspondence among the associates and trainees were desktop computers, laptop computers, computer tablets, personal digital assistant, enterprise digital assistant and very few other which were not common. Figure 1 reveals that all the associates and trainees used smart phones to connect to the internet as well as communicate with their colleagues. Desktop computers and laptop computers served only their alternatives in this enterprise as Figure 1 depicted only 20% of them utilized both devices.

Figure 1.
Participants' profile

Overall, this research sought to uncover the association between social media culture among associates and trainees affect their performance in the workplace. Specifically, it investigated the manner in which social media culture was propagated in this multicultural organization, the means where the online members' participation translated into tangible actions, the reasons for the emergence of the culture investigated and the value added it had to probable organizational communication.

With regards to propagation of social media culture, it was organically created at this automobile training industry, a multicultural organization through on-line interactions among associates mostly instructors themselves, among the trainees themselves and between the associates and the trainees in utility mostly of their smart phones. The majority of the instructors and trainees used their smart phones to connect to the internet as shown in Figure 1. Instructors utilized social media to form groups for their respective advisory classes for the purpose of not only creating an interactive environment for the trainees but also for information dissemination and file sharing required in their lessons. Almost all classes have their respective WhatsApp groups in order to monitor the trainees in terms of their performance in school. WhatsApp is also used as alternative submission of outputs for quizzes, examinations and other projects. Aside from their official WhatsApp groups, trainees create another group in WhatsApp for study help. This is the reason why most of the instructors and trainees use WhatsApp mobile application as shown in Figure 1 above.

Figure 2 shows that a great majority of the associates and the trainees always used social media platforms for communication and collaboration within this multicultural organization. On the other hand, 17% of them, sometimes did, 11% never did and the rest of the 1% rarely did. According to the associates and trainees the reason for this was the ease of correspondence via the social media platforms.

Figure 2.

Frequency of social media use for communication and collaboration

Figure 3 reveals that almost all associates and trainees had both WhatsApp and YouTube accounts, which they almost always used for work-related activities. On the other hand, a big majority of them had Snapchat while 32% had Instagram, 22% had Twitter, 17% had Telegram and 15% had Facebook. Indeed, WhatsApp and YouTube proved the most popular social media platforms among workers which was also mentioned by Muhammad (2023) in addition to Facebook.

Figure 3.

Common social media

Figure 4 illustrates how the associates, and the trainees described the social media culture within this multicultural organization. 47% of them described it as

diverse, 27% considered it inclusive, 16% thought it was collaborative and the rest of the 11% regarded it as competitive. This manifested the flexibility of social media in accepting diversity in different social media platforms.

Figure 4.

Description of social media culture

In fact, Figure 5 unveils that almost half of the associates and trainees perceived that the role of social media was very effective in promoting diversity and inclusion within their multicultural organization, while the other 41% observed it somewhat effective and only 12% were skeptical. Undeniably, social media is discerned to be effective in terms of diversity and inclusion promotion.

Figure 5.

Effectiveness of social media in promoting diversity and inclusion

Figure 6 demonstrates that a big majority of the associates and the trainees believed to a great extent that social media platforms contributed to fostering cross-

cultural understanding and collaboration within your organization. Only 33% of them had an idea that it was only to a certain extent and the rest of the 8% were convinced it to be only to a very small extent. Overall, the data indicates that the majority of associates and trainees have a positive perception of social media platforms' role in fostering cross-cultural understanding and collaboration, while acknowledging varying degrees of impact.

Figure 6.

Extent to which social media fostered cross-cultural understanding and collaboration

The foregoing data was supported by Figure 7, which elucidates that two-thirds of the associates and trainees claimed that social media platforms could be better utilized to enhance cross-cultural communication and collaboration within their organization. Conversely, 34% of them were against. The data suggests a divided perspective among associates and trainees regarding the potential of social media platforms for enhancing cross-cultural communication and collaboration within the organization. While a significant portion sees room for improvement and recognizes the untapped potential, a notable percentage remains skeptical or unconvinced of the effectiveness of social media in this context.

Figure 7.

Social media enhances cross-cultural communication and collaboration

Figure 8 enumerates the potential benefits and drawbacks of relying on social media for communication and collaboration in a multicultural organization. For possible benefits, half of the associates and trainees assessed that it could build relationships recognizing social media to be used for more than just brand-customer interaction. A few of them claimed that could share their expertise since they were given the chance to talk about what they know and what they want to be recognized for on social media. Also, a few of them discerned that with it they could connect anytime. Very few of them acknowledged that it could increase visibility and educate themselves too. For the drawbacks a few of them suggested that it not only could lack emotional connection but also decrease face-to-face communication skills. Very few of them discerned that it could give people a license to hurtful, convey inauthentic expression of feeling, diminish understanding and thoughtfulness and facilitate laziness. The data highlights a range of perspectives on the potential benefits and drawbacks of using social media for communication and collaboration in a multicultural organization. While some associates and trainees recognize the positive aspects such as relationship-building, expertise sharing, and accessibility, others express concerns about emotional disconnection, reduced face-to-face interaction, and negative behavioral tendencies

facilitated by social media platforms. Understanding and addressing these viewpoints can help organizations make informed decisions about leveraging social media effectively while mitigating potential drawbacks.

Figure 8.

Potential benefits of relying on social media for communication and collaboration

According to Figure 9, there were almost no specific social media practices or norms that had been adopted within the multicultural organization to enhance communication and collaboration. The data suggests that the organization as a whole has not implemented any structured or formalized approaches using social media platforms for these purposes. Almost all of the respondents denied the existence of such practices or norms within their organization.

However, during interviews, the majority of the respondents admitted using WhatsApp groups for the enhancement of communication and collaboration. This indicates that while there may not be formalized practices or norms related to social media, individuals within the organization have informally adopted WhatsApp groups

as a means to improve communication and collaboration. WhatsApp groups are likely being utilized as a convenient and accessible tool for sharing information, discussing work-related matters, and coordinating activities among team members.

The data suggests a discrepancy between the lack of formalized social media practices or norms in the organization and the informal use of WhatsApp groups for communication and collaboration. It implies that while the organization may not have implemented a broader strategy or guidelines for utilizing social media, individuals have independently adopted WhatsApp as a tool to facilitate their interactions. Understanding and acknowledging this informal usage can provide insights for the organization to develop and implement more structured approaches to leverage social media platforms effectively for communication and collaboration purposes.

Figure 9.

Existence of specific social media practices or norms

Figure 10 indicates the level of comfort that associates and trainees within the multicultural organization feel when expressing their cultural identity and perspectives through social media.

A significant majority of the respondents reported feeling somewhat comfortable in expressing their cultural identity and perspectives through social media. This suggests that a substantial portion of the associates and trainees feel at least moderately at ease when sharing aspects of their cultural background and personal viewpoints on social media platforms.

Approximately 22% of the respondents indicated that they feel very comfortable expressing their cultural identity and perspectives through social media. This subset of individuals feels highly at ease in using social media as a means to showcase their cultural background and express their perspectives within the organizational context.

On the other hand, around 20% of the respondents reported feeling not comfortable expressing their cultural identity and perspectives through social media. This group of individuals may experience reservations, concerns, or discomfort about sharing aspects of their cultural identity or personal opinions on social media platforms within the multicultural organization.

The data suggests that while a majority of the associates and trainees feel somewhat comfortable expressing their cultural identity and perspectives through social media, there is variability in the level of comfort among the respondents. The existence of a significant proportion of individuals who feel very comfortable indicates a positive environment where cultural expression is embraced. However, the presence of a subgroup that feels uncomfortable highlights the need for fostering inclusivity, understanding, and sensitivity to create an environment where all individuals feel safe and supported in expressing their cultural identity and perspectives through social media platforms within the organization.

Figure 10.

Comfortability to express cultural identity and perspective through social media

Figure 11 reveals that the majority of associates and trainees within the organization did not observe any instances where social media interactions had led to misunderstandings or cultural conflicts.

The data suggests that, from the perspective of the respondents, social media usage within the organization has not resulted in significant issues related to misunderstandings or conflicts arising from cultural differences.

It implies that the organization has been successful in navigating potential challenges related to cultural diversity in the context of social media interactions. The absence of reported instances of misunderstandings or cultural conflicts in social media interactions indicates a positive environment where individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds can engage with one another respectfully and effectively on these platforms.

The data suggests that, overall, social media interactions within the organization have been relatively free from misunderstandings or conflicts related to cultural differences. However, it is important to note that this data reflects the observations and perceptions of the associates and trainees. It is possible that there have been occasional instances of such conflicts that were not observed or reported

by the respondents. Continuous efforts to promote cultural understanding, open communication, and respectful engagement on social media platforms can further contribute to maintaining a harmonious and inclusive environment within the organization.

Figure 11.

Observation on social media interaction which led to misunderstanding and cultural conflict

Figure 12 shows that a majority of the associates and trainees within the multicultural organization believed that social media platforms are very effective in promoting cultural exchange and knowledge sharing.

The data indicates that a significant portion of the respondents expressed a strong belief in the effectiveness of social media platforms as a means to facilitate cultural exchange and sharing of knowledge within the organization.

Approximately 35% of the respondents indicated that they found social media platforms somewhat effective in promoting cultural exchange and knowledge sharing. This suggests that while they acknowledge the potential of social media for these purposes, they may have some reservations or perceive room for improvement.

On the other hand, around 12% of the respondents did not believe that social media platforms are effective in promoting cultural exchange and knowledge sharing within the organization. This group may hold the view that social media is not an effective tool for fostering cultural understanding or sharing knowledge in their specific organizational context.

The data suggests that the majority of associates and trainees have a positive perception of the effectiveness of social media platforms in promoting cultural exchange and knowledge sharing within the multicultural organization. This indicates that these individuals view social media as a valuable tool for fostering cross-cultural understanding and facilitating the sharing of diverse perspectives and insights. However, it is worth noting that there is a subset of respondents who hold more mixed or negative views about the effectiveness of social media for these purposes. Addressing the concerns of this subgroup and further enhancing the use of social media platforms to promote cultural exchange and knowledge sharing can contribute to fostering a more inclusive and collaborative organizational environment.

Figure 12.

Social media in promoting cultural exchange and knowledge sharing

Figure 13 unravels a larger proportion of associates and trainees felt that their organization did not provide sufficient guidelines or training on using social media platforms in a multicultural context.

The data suggests that these individuals perceive a lack of clear instructions or training from their organization on how to effectively navigate social media platforms when engaging with diverse cultures.

It is important to note that some associates who were interviewed stated that the organization always provided clear guidelines on social media usage from the beginning, indicating that there are instances where organizations do lay down the guidelines upfront.

However, there were also other associates who admitted that the organization failed to provide sufficient guidelines on social media usage in a multicultural context.

The data highlights a potential gap in the organization's approach to preparing associates and trainees for the challenges and opportunities that arise from using social media in a multicultural setting.

The data suggests that, overall, there is a perceived lack of adequate guidelines or training provided by the organization regarding the usage of social media platforms in a multicultural context. While some associates reported that such guidelines were established at the outset, the presence of individuals who admitted to a lack of guidelines suggests a need for improvement in this area. Enhancing the provision of clear guidelines and comprehensive training can help associates and trainees navigate social media platforms effectively, ensuring that they engage with cultural awareness, sensitivity, and inclusivity. This can contribute to creating a positive and harmonious multicultural environment within the organization.

Figure 13.

Provision of guidelines on the usage of social media

Figure 14 explains that the majority of associates and trainees did not encounter any challenges or barriers when using social media platforms to communicate with colleagues from different cultural backgrounds.

The data suggests that these individuals found it relatively easy and seamless to use social media platforms as a means of communication, regardless of cultural differences. It indicates a high level of success in using social media for cross-cultural communication within the organization.

The findings imply that the associates and trainees are comfortable and proficient in leveraging social media platforms to interact with colleagues from diverse cultural backgrounds.

This positive outcome suggests that the organizations multicultural environment and the associates' and the trainees' digital skills are conducive to effective cross-cultural communication through social media.

The data indicates that the majority of associates and trainees did not face challenges or barriers when using social media platforms to communicate with colleagues from different cultural backgrounds. This suggests that these individuals were able to navigate cultural differences and effectively connect with their colleagues

through social media. The findings highlight the success and ease of using social media as a tool for fostering cross-cultural communication within the organization. It also indicates that the associates and trainees possess the necessary digital skills and cultural competence to engage in effective communication across diverse cultures.

Figure 14.

Presence of challenges in social media communication with colleagues

Figure 15 showcases how social media platforms could be leveraged to celebrate and showcase the diverse cultures and backgrounds within their organization.

Approximately half of the associates and trainees acknowledged that social media platforms in some way encouraged employees to connect and develop relationships with coworkers beyond their immediate circle. This indicates that these individuals perceive social media as a tool that facilitates interaction and bonding between colleagues from different cultural backgrounds.

However, a notable portion of the respondents (27%) asserted that social media platforms did, in fact, facilitate such connections and bonding. On the other hand, a smaller percentage of associates and trainees (15%) did not affirm that

social media platforms had a positive impact on fostering connections and bonding among employees from diverse backgrounds.

Overall, the data suggests that a significant portion of the associates and trainees perceive social media platforms as a means to promote connections and bonding among employees from different cultural backgrounds. However, there are still some individuals who may not share this sentiment or feel that social media platforms do not have a significant impact in this regard. It implies the potential for leveraging social media more effectively to celebrate and showcase diversity within the organization and foster stronger connections among employees. Organizations could explore strategies to maximize the positive effects of social media platforms in promoting cross-cultural interaction and fostering a sense of unity among employees from diverse backgrounds.

Figure 15.

Social media leverage to celebrate and showcase the diverse cultures and backgrounds within the organization

Figure 16 suggests that the social media culture within an organization has a significant impact on overall organizational performance and productivity in a

multicultural context. Almost all of the associates and trainees (nearly 100%) were assertive about the impact of social media culture in this regard.

The data indicates a strong consensus among the respondents that the use of social media platforms and the cultural norms surrounding their use have a positive influence on the organization's performance and productivity in a multicultural setting. This suggests that the associates and trainees perceive social media culture as a valuable asset that enhances communication, collaboration, and knowledge sharing across different cultural backgrounds. The findings imply that the organization has successfully established a social media culture that fosters inclusivity, engagement, and effective cross-cultural communication, leading to improved performance and productivity.

Overall, the data highlights the positive perception of associates and trainees regarding the impact of social media culture on organizational performance and productivity in a multicultural context. It indicates that the organization's emphasis on social media and its integration into the cultural fabric of the organization has yielded significant benefits. The findings underscore the importance of nurturing a positive and inclusive social media culture to enhance communication, collaboration, and overall organizational success in a diverse environment.

Figure 16.

Impact of social media culture on performance and productivity

As regards how online members' participation translated in action, Figure 17 unfolds the ways in which active engagement on social media platforms translates into real-life action among associates and trainees.

The majority of the respondents reported volunteering for a cause as a result of their engagement on social media platforms. This indicates that a significant number of associates and trainees were motivated to take tangible actions and contribute their time and efforts to support causes they care about after being exposed to information and discussions on social media. Additionally, approximately 30% of the respondents reported supporting charitable organizations financially. This suggests that a considerable portion of the associates and trainees were inspired to make financial contributions to organizations or causes they came across through their social media engagement. The remaining respondents indicated that they participated in rallies or protests or engaged in other activities as a result of their social media involvement. This data suggests that some respondents were motivated to participate in offline activities and events, potentially driven by the information, discussions, and connections they made through social media platforms.

Overall, the data demonstrates that active engagement on social media platforms has a significant impact on translating virtual interactions into real-life action among associates and trainees. It indicates that social media serves as a catalyst for inspiring individuals to volunteer, support charitable organizations, participate in rallies or protests, and engage in other activities related to causes they are passionate about. This highlights the potential of social media platforms to mobilize and activate individuals, leading to meaningful contributions and participation in real-world events and initiatives.

Figure 17.

Active engagement on social media translated into real-life action

Figure 18 confirms that a majority of the associates and trainees reported taking action based on the content they saw or interacted with on social media platforms.

It is stated that they constitute the majority. This indicates that a significant number of the respondents were influenced by the content they encountered on social media and subsequently engaged in some form of action as a result. Additionally, 21% of the respondents reported occasionally taking action based on social media content, while another 21% stated that they rarely or never took action. This suggests that there is a portion of associates and trainees who are more passive or less inclined to act based on the content they consume on social media. The data implies that while the majority of the respondents were motivated to take action, there is still a notable percentage who either only occasionally took action or rarely/never did so.

Overall, the data indicates that a significant majority of associates and trainees took action based on the content they encountered on social media platforms. However, there is also a notable portion that is less inclined to act or only occasionally

takes action in response to social media content. This highlights the varying degrees of impact that social media has on motivating individuals to take tangible actions. It is important to consider factors such as individual motivation, personal values, and the nature of the content itself when assessing the influence of social media on driving action.

Figure 18.

Frequency of action taken on content

Figure 19 presents the factors that motivated social media users, specifically associates and trainees, to convert their online engagement into tangible actions.

The majority of the respondents stated that the influence or encouragement from friends or peers was the primary factor that motivated them to take action. This suggests that social connections and social influence play a significant role in inspiring individuals to translate their online engagement into real-life actions. The data indicates that associates and trainees are more likely to be motivated by the support and encouragement they receive from people within their social circles. Additionally, the remaining respondents stated that their emotional connection to the cause was the motivating factor for taking action. This implies that personal connection and empathy towards a cause or issue played a vital role in driving individuals to convert their online

engagement into tangible actions. Also, the data suggests that both social influence and personal emotional connection are important motivators for these respondents.

Overall, the data highlights the significance of social connections and emotional connections in motivating associates and trainees to convert their online engagement on social media into tangible actions. The influence and encouragement from friends or peers play a major role in inspiring individuals to take action, while personal emotional connection to the cause also serves as a strong motivator. This emphasizes the importance of social relationships and personal values in driving individuals to actively participate and contribute to causes they care about.

Figure 19.

Motivation of social media users

Figure 20 signifies the perceptions of associates and trainees regarding the effectiveness of social media platforms in initiating or facilitating real-life action.

The majority of the respondents validated social media platforms as effective means for initiating or facilitating real-life action. This indicates that a significant number of associates and trainees believe that social media platforms are effective

tools for translating online engagement into tangible actions in the real world. The data suggests that these individuals recognize the potential of social media platforms to mobilize and inspire people to take concrete steps or participate in activities related to a cause or issue. Additionally, only 15% of the respondents invalidated social media platforms as effective means for initiating or facilitating real-life action. This implies that a small percentage of associates and trainees are skeptical about the effectiveness of social media platforms in driving real-life action. The data indicates that the majority of the respondents have a positive perception regarding the role of social media platforms in enabling and encouraging real-world engagement.

Overall, the data suggests that most associates and trainees perceive social media platforms as effective means for initiating or facilitating real-life action. They acknowledge the potential of these platforms in mobilizing individuals and driving them to take tangible actions. However, a small percentage of respondents hold a negative perception and do not consider social media platforms as effective in facilitating real-life action. This highlights the varying perspectives among individuals regarding the role and effectiveness of social media platforms in driving meaningful engagement and action.

Figure 20.

Perception on social media

Figure 21 itemizes the kinds of actions most commonly taken by social media users who were motivated by the content they saw and engaged with online.

About two-thirds of the associates and trainees donated to charitable causes: This implies that a significant majority (approximately 66.67%) of the associates and trainees who engaged with online content felt motivated to contribute financially to charitable organizations. It indicates a strong inclination towards supporting causes through monetary means.

16% signed petitions or supported online campaigns: Approximately 16% of the social media users who were motivated by the content they saw and engaged with online chose to express their support by signing petitions or actively participating in online campaigns. This suggests that a notable portion of users prefers to engage in advocacy efforts by adding their voices to organized campaigns or initiatives.

The remainder participated in online activism or other activities: The remaining portion of social media users who were motivated by online content engaged in online activism or other activities. This category encompasses a diverse range of actions that users may have taken, which could include sharing informative content, raising awareness about specific issues, engaging in discussions, or supporting local community initiatives. The specific breakdown of these activities is not provided in the data.

Overall, the data indicates that a significant portion of the social media users in question demonstrated an active response to the content they encountered online. They either donated to charitable causes, signed petitions or supported online campaigns, or engaged in various forms of online activism or other activities. This

suggests a strong level of engagement and motivation among these users to make a positive impact based on the content they consumed on social media platforms.

Figure 21.

Actions taken by social media users

Figure 22 discloses the level of active participation in discussions or conversations on social media platforms among associates and trainees.

Great majority of associates and trainees sometimes actively participated in discussions or conversations: This indicates that a significant majority (more than half) of the associates and trainees reported engaging in discussions or conversations on social media platforms at least occasionally. They were willing to actively contribute their thoughts, opinions, or ideas in online discussions.

The rest of them either always or rarely participated. The remaining portion of associates and trainees fell into two categories. Some of them reported always participating in discussions or conversations on social media platforms, suggesting a consistent and highly engaged approach to online interactions. On the other hand,

there were those who rarely participated, indicating a lower frequency of engagement in online discussions or conversations.

Overall, the data highlights that a majority of the associates and trainees had a tendency to actively participate in discussions or conversations on social media platforms. This suggests that they were interested in exchanging ideas, expressing their opinions, or engaging in conversations with others on topics of interest. However, there were also individuals who either consistently participated or rarely participated, indicating variations in the level of engagement among this group.

Figure 22.

Frequency of online members' active participation in discussions or conversations on social media platforms

Figure 23 connotes the relationship between the participation of associates and trainees on social media platforms and the resulting tangible actions or outcomes within their organization.

Majority of the associates' and trainees' participation on social media platforms translated into tangible actions or outcomes within their organization to a certain extent: This indicates that a significant majority (more than half) of the associates and trainees reported that their engagement on social media platforms had some level of impact or resulted in tangible actions within their organization. The data does not specify the exact nature of these actions or outcomes, but it implies that their participation played a role in driving positive changes or producing measurable results.

38% of the associates' and trainees' participation translated to a great extent: Approximately 38% of respondents reported that their participation on social media platforms had a significant impact on their organization. This suggests that their engagement played a substantial role in driving notable actions or outcomes within their workplace.

7% of the associates' and trainees' participation translated to a very small extent: On the other hand, a small portion (7%) of respondents indicated that their participation on social media platforms had only minimal impact or resulted in very few tangible actions within their organization. This suggests that their engagement had limited influence on driving significant changes or outcomes.

Overall, the data indicates that a majority of the associates and trainees reported that their participation on social media platforms had some degree of impact or resulted in tangible actions within their organization. A significant percentage felt that their engagement had a great extent of impact, while a smaller percentage felt that it had a very small extent of impact. This suggests that there is a relationship between their social media participation and the outcomes within the organization, with a varying level of effectiveness among the respondents.

Figure 23.

Extent to which participation on social media platforms translates into tangible actions or outcomes within the organization

Figure 24 unfurls the level of active participation in discussions or conversations on social media platforms among associates and trainees.

The majority of the associates and trainees sometimes actively participate in discussions or conversations. This indicates that a significant majority (more than half) of the associates and trainees reported engaging in discussions or conversations on social media platforms at least occasionally. They actively contribute their thoughts, opinions, or ideas in online discussions on a periodic basis.

Twice the number of associates and trainees who never participated always did. This indicates that there is a notable difference between the number of individuals who never participated in discussions or conversations on social media platforms and those who always did. Specifically, the number of individuals who always participated was twice that of those who never participated. This suggests that there is a significant group of individuals who consistently engage in discussions or conversations on social

media platforms, regardless of the frequency or extent of participation reported by the majority.

Overall, the data highlights that a majority of the associates and trainees reported participating in discussions or conversations on social media platforms at least sometimes. However, there is a significant subset of individuals who consistently engage in these activities, even if the majority only participate periodically. The data suggests that there is a range of engagement levels among the associates and trainees when it comes to participating in discussions or conversations on social media platforms.

Figure 24.

Members contribution of innovative ideas or solutions

Figure 25 substantiates that none of the associates and trainees reported observing any instances where their participation on social media platforms resulted in the implementation of new initiatives within their organization.

None of the associates and trainees observed instances of their social media participation leading to new initiatives: The data suggests that there was no reported evidence or observation among the associates and trainees of their engagement on social media platforms directly resulting in the implementation of new initiatives within their organization. This means that their participation did not lead to the introduction of novel projects, programs, or significant changes in their workplace.

Overall, the data indicates a lack of perceived impact or connection between the participation of the associates and trainees on social media platforms and the implementation of new initiatives within their organization. It suggests that, based on their observations, their engagement on social media did not directly lead to the introduction of new projects or significant changes in their workplace.

Figure 25.

Observation of instances where online members' participation on social media platforms led to the implementation of new projects or initiatives within the organization

Figure 26 authenticates that a large majority of the associates and trainees reported that their participation on social media platforms was somewhat effective in

driving decision-making processes within their organization. Additionally, a smaller portion of respondents stated that they believed it to be even very effective.

Big majority reported their participation as somewhat effective. The data indicates that a significant majority of the associates and trainees expressed that their engagement on social media platforms had some level of effectiveness in influencing decision-making processes within their organization. This suggests that they believed their contributions, opinions, or discussions on social media had a noticeable impact on decision-making, although the extent of that impact might vary.

The rest corroborated it to be very effective: In addition to the majority, a smaller portion of the respondents reported that they believed their participation on social media platforms to be even very effective in driving decision-making processes. This suggests that these individuals perceived a strong influence and impact of their engagement on social media platforms on the decisions made within their organization.

Overall, the data indicates that a significant majority of the associates and trainees felt that their participation on social media platforms had at least some level of effectiveness in driving decision-making processes within their organization. This suggests that they believed their engagement on social media had an impact on the decision-making culture, although the extent of that impact varied. The data also highlights that a portion of respondents perceived their participation on social media to be even very effective in influencing decisions.

Figure 26.

Effectiveness of online members' participation on social media platforms in driving decision-making processes within the organization

Figure 27 explicates that a large majority of the associates and trainees reported that their participation on social media platforms influenced the overall organizational culture and values to a certain extent. Out of these respondents, 33% stated that their influence was significant (*to a great extent*), while only 8% reported a minimal influence (*to a very small extent*).

Big majority reported their influence as to a certain extent. The data suggests that a significant majority of the associates and trainees believed that their engagement on social media platforms had an influence on the overall organizational culture and values. This indicates that they perceived their participation to have some impact on shaping the cultural aspects and values within their organization, although the extent of that influence varied among individuals.

33% reported their influence to a great extent. Within the majority, a notable proportion (33%) indicated that their participation on social media had a significant influence (*to a great extent*) on the overall organizational culture and values. This

suggests that these individuals felt that their engagement had a substantial impact on shaping the cultural aspects and values of their organization.

Only 8% reported a very small extent of influence. In contrast, a small percentage (8%) of respondents stated that their participation on social media had a minimal influence (*to a very small extent*) on the overall organizational culture and values. This implies that these individuals perceived their engagement to have a limited impact on shaping the cultural aspects and values within their organization.

Overall, the data signifies that a significant majority of the associates and trainees felt that their participation on social media platforms influenced the overall organizational culture and values to a certain extent. It highlights a range of perceptions, with some reporting a significant influence and others perceiving a minimal impact.

Figure 27.

Extent to which online members' participation on social media platforms influenced the overall organizational culture and values

Figure 28 unrolls that all the associates and trainees did not observe any differences in the level of action or implementation resulting from their participation on social media platforms across different teams or departments within their organization.

Lack of differences noticed. The data indicates that none of the associates and trainees reported noticing any variations or discrepancies in the level of action or implementation that occurred as a result of their participation on social media platforms when comparing different teams or departments within their organization. This suggests that, according to their perception, the impact of their engagement on social media was consistent across the organization, regardless of the specific team or department involved.

Overall, the data suggests that the associates and trainees did not observe any discernible differences in the level of action or implementation resulting from their participation on social media platforms across various teams or departments within their organization. This implies that, from their perspective, the influence or outcomes of their engagement on social media were similar and consistent throughout the organization.

Figure 28.

Differences in the level of action or implementation resulting from online members' participation on social media platforms across different teams or departments within the organization

Figure 29 interprets the level of accountability and follow-through exhibited by online members after participating in discussions or activities on social media platforms.

Almost half of the associates and trainees reported being actively engaged after their interactions on social media. This suggests that they took responsibility for their actions and showed a proactive approach in following through with their engagement.

The other half of the associates and trainees (50%) reported being passive in their participation. Within this group, 37% expressed a desire to be observed, indicating that they preferred to observe or monitor discussions and activities rather than actively contribute. The remaining 13% expressed a desire to be evaluated, suggesting that they wanted their contributions to be assessed or reviewed by others.

Overall, the data indicates a fairly balanced distribution between active and passive participation among the associates and trainees. Approximately half of them were actively engaged, while the other half exhibited passive behavior, with varying preferences for observation or evaluation. This suggests that individuals may have different motivations and expectations regarding their involvement on social media platforms.

Figure 29.

Level of accountability and follow-through

The characteristics that helped online members successfully translate their social media engagement into worthwhile action within their organization are shown in Figure 30.

According to 37% of the associates and trainees, evaluating business goals was identified as a contributing factor to the success of translating social media engagement into worthwhile action. This suggests that understanding and aligning social media efforts with the overall goals of the organization played a significant role in achieving positive outcomes.

18% of the associates and trainees believed that identifying the target audience was an important factor. This indicates that having a clear understanding of the audience they wanted to reach and engage with on social media platforms helped them in achieving success.

14% of the associates and trainees recognized the importance of selecting the right social media platforms. This suggests that choosing the platforms that align with the target audience and provide effective channels for communication and engagement was crucial for their success.

The data also indicates that a smaller percentage of the associates and trainees believed that analyzing the competition, creating a compelling content strategy, and allocating resources were important factors in translating social media engagement into worthwhile action. Although these factors were mentioned by a smaller percentage, they still contribute to the overall success.

Overall, the data highlights the significance of evaluating business goals, identifying the target audience, and selecting effective social media platforms in

successfully leveraging social media engagement for meaningful impact within an organization. Additionally, factors such as analyzing the competition, creating compelling content, and allocating resources also play a role, although they were mentioned by a smaller percentage of the respondents.

Figure 30.

Factors contributing to successful translation of online members' participation in social media platforms into meaningful action within the organization

Figure 31 discloses that the majority of associates and trainees did not perceive any significant barriers or challenges that hindered the translation of online members' participation on social media platforms into concrete actions or outcomes within their organization.

This suggests that a high percentage of associates and trainees held a positive view regarding the translation of online members' engagement on social media. They believed that the participation of online members seamlessly translated into tangible actions and outcomes within their organization.

It indicates that the respondents did not identify any specific obstacles or challenges that hindered the conversion of online participation into concrete actions. This suggests that they did not perceive factors such as limited resources, organizational resistance, or lack of strategic alignment as significant barriers.

The overall interpretation of the data suggests that the online members' engagement on social media platforms was perceived as being easily integrated and translated into meaningful actions within the organization. This positive perception may indicate that the necessary support structures, processes, and resources were in place to facilitate this seamless transition.

It is important to note that the data specifically highlights the perspectives of the associates and trainees, and other stakeholders within the organization may have different views or experiences. Nevertheless, the data suggests that, from the perspective of this particular group, the translation of online members' participation on social media into concrete actions or outcomes within their organization was perceived as largely unimpeded by barriers or challenges.

Figure 31.

Barriers or challenges that hinder the translation of online members' participation on social media platforms into concrete actions or outcomes within the organization

Figure 32 indicates how leadership within their organization supported or encouraged online members' participation on social media platforms to drive action and implementation.

The majority of associates and trainees believed that the leaders in their organization were at least somewhat supportive of online members' participation on social media platforms. This suggests that there was a general level of support from leadership for engaging with social media as a means to drive action and implementation.

The data indicates that a significant portion, 26%, of the respondents believed that their leaders were very supportive. This subset of associates and trainees perceived strong encouragement and active support from their leaders in utilizing social media platforms for driving action and implementation.

While the majority of respondents perceived some level of support from their leaders, there were still a few who believed that their leaders were not supportive at all. This indicates that there may have been a small segment within the organization where leaders were not actively encouraging or endorsing online members' participation on social media.

Overall, the data suggests that there was a generally positive perception of leadership support for online members' engagement on social media platforms to drive action and implementation. However, it's worth noting that while most respondents felt at least somewhat supported, a significant portion perceived strong support, and a small minority felt a lack of support from their leaders. These varying perceptions may be influenced by factors such as individual experiences, organizational culture, or the

specific strategies employed by leadership to encourage and facilitate social media engagement.

Figure 32.

Driving action and implementation support

The data from Figure 33 indicates that the associates and trainees believed that there were no specific strategies or initiatives implemented within their organization to bridge the gap between online participation on social media platforms and tangible actions.

According to the respondents, there was a perceived absence of targeted strategies or initiatives within their organization aimed at effectively connecting online participation on social media platforms with tangible actions. This suggests that the organization may not have implemented specific measures or programs to guide and facilitate the translation of online engagement into concrete outcomes.

The lack of specific strategies or initiatives to bridge the gap between online participation and tangible actions may have several implications. It could mean that the organization has not recognized the importance of leveraging social media engagement for driving real-world results or that they have not prioritized the development and implementation of such strategies.

The data suggests that there is an opportunity for the organization to explore and adopt strategies that can enhance the translation of online participation into tangible actions. By implementing targeted initiatives, such as creating clear action plans, providing resources and support, or establishing feedback mechanisms, the organization can better align online engagement with their desired outcomes.

It is important to note that the data reflects the perceived absence of specific strategies or initiatives from the perspective of the associates and trainees. However, there may be existing efforts or plans within the organization that were not captured by this particular survey. Further investigation and dialogue with other stakeholders and leadership would be necessary to gain a comprehensive understanding of the organization's approach to bridging the gap between online participation on social media platforms and tangible actions.

Figure 33.

Strategies to bridge the gap between online participation in social media platforms and tangible actions

Figure 34 specifies what role effective communication played in ensuring that online members' participation on social media platforms leads to concrete actions or outcomes within their organization.

According to the associates and trainees, effective communication played a crucial role in building employee morale, satisfaction, and engagement. Clear and open communication channels were seen as essential for fostering a positive work environment and improving overall employee well-being and commitment.

The data suggests that effective communication was also seen as important in educating employees about the benefits of remaining union-free, aligning with the organization's goal. By effectively conveying the merits and advantages of not joining a union, the organization aimed to engage employees and encourage them to support the organization's stance.

The data indicates that effective communication was recognized as a means of giving employees a voice and empowering them within the organization. By providing opportunities for employees to express their opinions and concerns, the organization aimed to enhance employee satisfaction and create a culture of open dialogue and mutual respect.

The associates and trainees believed that effective communication played a role in helping employees understand the terms and conditions of their employment. By facilitating clear communication about employment policies, benefits, and expectations, the organization sought to foster commitment and loyalty among employees.

Lastly, the data suggests that effective communication was seen as a way to reduce misunderstandings, grievances, and potential lawsuits within the organization. By improving communication channels and ensuring clarity in processes and

procedures, the organization aimed to enhance efficiency, reduce costs, and create a more harmonious work environment.

Overall, the data highlights the multifaceted role of effective communication in driving positive outcomes within the organization. From building employee morale and satisfaction to educating employees, giving them a voice, and improving processes, effective communication was considered crucial for achieving concrete actions and outcomes. This emphasizes the importance of establishing clear and transparent communication practices within the organization to foster employee engagement, satisfaction, and overall organizational success.

Figure 34.

Role of effective communication

Figure 35 gauges the impact of online members' participation on social media platforms in driving action and achieving organizational goals. Half of the associates and trainees contended it was somewhat impactful while almost half of them argued it was very impactful. Only 4% of them insisted it was not impactful.

Based on the data presented in Figure 35, it can be observed that the impact of online members' participation on social media platforms in driving action and achieving organizational goals is perceived positively by a majority of the associates and trainees surveyed.

The data suggests that approximately half of the respondents contended that online members' participation on social media platforms was somewhat impactful in driving action and achieving organizational goals. This indicates that they recognized a moderate level of influence and contribution from online members in terms of driving desired actions and helping the organization achieve its goals. While they acknowledged a positive impact, it is possible that they felt there was still potential for further improvement or more substantial contributions.

Nearly half of the respondents argued that online members' participation on social media platforms was very impactful. This indicates that they believed online members played a significant role in driving action and actively contributing to the achievement of organizational goals through their participation on social media platforms. Their perception suggests that online members' engagement and involvement had a substantial influence on the organization's success.

Only a small percentage (4%) of the respondents insisted that online members' participation on social media platforms was not impactful. This suggests that they

perceived minimal or no meaningful impact from online members' engagement on social media in driving action or helping the organization achieve its goals. It is important to consider their perspective and understand the reasons behind their negative assessment to identify areas for improvement or address any challenges or obstacles that may be hindering the impact of online members' participation.

Overall, the data indicates that a significant majority of the associates and trainees perceive online members' participation on social media platforms as impactful in driving action and achieving organizational goals. This highlights the importance of cultivating active engagement and involvement of online members and leveraging their contributions to drive desired outcomes and organizational success.

Figure 35.

Impact in driving action and achieving organizational goals

Figure 36 rolls what improvements or changes the associates and trainees suggested that should enhance the translation of online members' participation on social media platforms into tangible actions or outcomes within their organization.

The associates and trainees suggested that consistent and regular activity on social media platforms is essential. This indicates the importance of actively engaging with online members through posting updates, sharing content, and initiating conversations. By being consistently active, the organization can maintain a strong online presence and encourage ongoing participation.

The suggestion to unblock social media platforms like Facebook, YouTube, and other important social network sites highlights the need to remove any restrictions that prevent access to these platforms. By unblocking social media sites, the organization allows for active social participation and enables members to engage more freely. This can lead to increased interaction and better utilization of these platforms.

The data suggests that using the right tools is crucial for effectively managing online engagement. This could refer to employing social media management tools, analytics platforms, or other resources that facilitate monitoring and optimizing online activities. By utilizing appropriate tools, the organization can streamline their efforts and ensure efficient management of their social media presence.

The suggestion to check current trends emphasizes the need to stay updated with the latest developments in social media and online engagement. By monitoring trends, the organization can adapt their strategies to align with current best practices and capitalize on emerging opportunities. This proactive approach can help them stay relevant and maximize the impact of their online participation.

The data indicates that incorporating multimedia content, such as images, videos, and other visual elements, is recommended to enhance online engagement. By utilizing multimedia, the organization can make their communications more

engaging, visually appealing, and shareable. This can attract the attention of online members and increase the likelihood of driving actions or desired outcomes.

The suggestion to evaluate results underscores the importance of measuring the effectiveness of online engagement efforts. By regularly assessing the outcomes and analyzing data, the organization can identify areas for improvement and make informed decisions to optimize their strategies. Evaluating results enables them to refine their approach and ensure that their online participation aligns with their organizational goals.

The associates and trainees recommended actively interacting with online members. This suggests the significance of fostering two-way communication and engaging in conversations through comments, messages, and other forms of interaction. By actively interacting, the organization can strengthen relationships with members, address their concerns, gather feedback, and create a sense of community. It also provides an opportunity to humanize the brand and establish a personal connection with the audience. Actively interacting with online members can help build trust, loyalty, and a positive brand image. It allows the organization to understand the needs and preferences of its audience, leading to better decision-making and the development of tailored products or services.

Overall, the recommendation to actively interact with online members emphasizes the importance of building meaningful relationships and fostering open dialogue in the digital space.

Figure 36.

Improvements and changes

About the analysis of the reasons why the emerging culture was created, Figure 37 unravels the main motivation behind the emergence of social media culture.

Nearly half of the associates and trainees stated that their desire for increased connectivity was their primary motivation for engaging with social media. This suggests that they see social media platforms as a means to connect with others, whether it's staying in touch with friends and family, networking with professionals, or engaging in communities of interest. The ability to connect and communicate with a wide range of individuals and communities is a significant driving force behind their involvement in social media culture.

29% of the respondents identified their need for self-expression as a key motivator for participating in social media. This indicates that they view these platforms as a space to share their thoughts, ideas, opinions, and creativity with others. Social media provides a platform for individuals to express their identities, showcase their talents, and engage in self-representation. The desire for self-expression and the

opportunity to have a voice and be heard are important factors driving their engagement with social media culture.

The remaining percentage of respondents (21%) attributed the emergence of social media culture to the influence of societal trends. This suggests that they perceive social media adoption and participation as a reflection of broader trends and societal shifts towards increased digital connectivity and online interaction. These individuals may feel that engaging with social media is expected or necessary to stay relevant in a rapidly evolving digital society. Their motivation is influenced by the belief that social media culture is a product of wider social and cultural changes.

Generally, this highlights that the emergence of social media culture is primarily driven by the desire for increased connectivity, the need for self-expression, and the influence of societal trends. These motivations reflect the importance of social interaction, individual expression, and staying connected in the digital age. Understanding these motivations can help organizations and individuals better tailor their social media strategies and content to effectively engage with the target audience and capitalize on the underlying motivations behind social media culture.

Figure 37.

Main motivation for the emergence of social media culture

Figure 38 enumerates the factors that played the most significant role in the creation of social media culture. The associates and trainees affirmed top three of those factors.

The most prominent factor identified by the respondents was the human need for connection. This suggests that the desire to connect with others, build relationships, and foster social interactions played a crucial role in the emergence of social media culture. Social media platforms provide individuals with a convenient and accessible means to connect and communicate with a wide range of people, regardless of geographical barriers. The innate human need for connection has been amplified and fulfilled through the advent of social media, influencing its creation and widespread adoption.

The second factor highlighted by the respondents is technological advancements. This indicates that the development and evolution of technology, particularly in the realm of digital communication and networking, significantly contributed to the formation of social media culture. The advancements in internet infrastructure, mobile devices, and digital platforms have facilitated the creation and widespread availability of social media platforms. These technological innovations have enabled the seamless sharing of information, multimedia content, and real-time interactions, fostering the growth and popularity of social media culture.

The final factor emphasized by the respondents is the desire for social validation. This suggests that the need for recognition, acceptance, and validation from others has played a significant role in shaping social media culture. Social media platforms provide individuals with opportunities to showcase their achievements, receive feedback, and gain social approval through likes, comments, and shares. The

desire for social validation has driven individuals to actively participate in social media culture, seeking affirmation and acknowledgment from their online networks.

Overall, the data from Figure 38 indicates that the creation of social media culture can be attributed to the human need for connection, technological advancements, and the desire for social validation. These factors highlight the fundamental aspects of human nature, the influence of technological progress, and the psychological motivations that have fueled the widespread adoption and impact of social media. Understanding these factors can help individuals and organizations navigate and harness the power of social media culture effectively.

Figure 38.

Factors for the creation of social media culture

Figure 39 showcases the reasons social media culture has become so influential in recent years.

The largest percentage of respondents (38%) identified the desire for instant gratification as a key reason for the significant influence of social media culture. This suggests that individuals are drawn to social media platforms because they offer

immediate rewards and satisfaction. Whether it's receiving likes, comments, or engaging in real-time interactions, social media provides instant feedback and gratification, fulfilling the human desire for instant validation and attention. The immediacy and quick response of social media contribute to its influence and addictive nature.

Approximately 29% of the respondents believed that the increasing accessibility to the internet has played a crucial role in the rise of social media culture. As internet connectivity becomes more widespread and affordable, more people have gained access to online platforms, including social media. Increased internet accessibility has expanded the user base and facilitated the engagement of individuals from diverse backgrounds and regions, contributing to the growth and influence of social media culture.

A significant portion of respondents (25%) highlighted the effectiveness of social media as a communication tool as a reason for its influence. Social media platforms provide convenient and efficient means of communication, allowing individuals to connect, share information, and engage with others on a global scale. The ability to communicate and interact with a large audience quickly and easily has made social media an influential medium for expressing ideas, disseminating information, and mobilizing communities.

In general, the data from Figure 39 suggests that the desire for instant gratification, increasing accessibility to the internet, and the effectiveness of social media as a communication tool are key factors contributing to the significant influence of social media culture. These factors highlight the appeal of immediate rewards, the expanding reach of online connectivity, and the power of social media as a

communication platform. Understanding these reasons can provide insights into the continued growth and impact of social media culture in recent years.

Figure 39.

Reasons for social media culture influence

Figure 40 discloses the impact of social media culture on traditional forms of communication, as perceived by associates and trainees.

The data indicates that a significant majority of respondents believed that social media culture has increased global connectivity. This suggests that social media platforms have played a vital role in connecting individuals from different parts of the world, breaking down geographical barriers and facilitating cross-cultural interactions. Social media has provided a platform for people to connect, communicate, and share information on a global scale, fostering a sense of interconnectedness and promoting global dialogue.

A notable percentage of respondents (16%) indicated that social media culture has led to a decrease in face-to-face interactions. This suggests that the prevalence of social media platforms may have reduced the frequency or quality of in-person interactions. People may be substituting face-to-face communication with online interactions, leading to a potential decline in traditional forms of direct, physical communication. However, it's important to note that this interpretation is based on the perspective of a specific group of respondents and may not represent the views of the broader population.

Another 16% of the respondents stated that social media culture has changed the way information is disseminated. This suggests that social media platforms have transformed the landscape of information sharing and distribution. Traditional forms of communication such as newspapers, radio, and television have been supplemented, and in some cases, replaced by social media as a primary source of news and information. Social media allows for rapid sharing of information, user-generated content, and real-time updates, altering the traditional dynamics of how information is accessed and consumed.

Overall, the data from Figure 40 indicates that social media culture has had various impacts on traditional forms of communication. It has increased global connectivity, potentially decreased face-to-face interactions, and changed the way information is disseminated. These findings highlight the transformative influence of social media on communication patterns and underscore the need to understand and adapt to the evolving communication landscape shaped by social media culture.

Figure 40.

Impact of social media culture on traditional forms of communication

Figure 41 delineates the impact of the emergence of social media culture on society as a whole, as perceived by associates and trainees.

The data indicates that a significant percentage of respondents (37%) believe that social media culture has significantly impacted business practices and marketing strategies. This suggests that social media platforms have revolutionized how businesses engage with customers, promote their products or services, and build brand awareness. Social media provides companies with new avenues to reach and interact with their target audience, allowing for more targeted advertising, personalized marketing campaigns, and direct customer engagement. The emergence of social media has forced businesses to adapt their practices and strategies to effectively utilize these platforms and stay competitive in the digital landscape.

A notable percentage of respondents (29%) asserted that social media culture has changed societal norms and values. This suggests that social media has influenced cultural and social dynamics, shaping the way people think, behave, and

interact with one another. Social media platforms provide a space for individuals to express their opinions, share their experiences, and participate in online discussions. This has contributed to the dissemination of new ideas, the amplification of certain perspectives, and the evolution of societal norms and values. However, it's important to note that societal norms and values are complex and can be influenced by various factors beyond social media alone.

Another 29% of respondents stated that the emergence of social media culture has led to increased awareness and activism. Social media has provided a platform for individuals and groups to raise awareness about social issues, share information, and mobilize communities for causes they care about. The ease of sharing information, organizing events, and connecting with like-minded individuals has empowered individuals to become more active and engaged in addressing societal challenges. Social media has facilitated the rapid spread of social movements, giving a voice to marginalized groups and driving conversations on important social issues.

In conclusion, the data from Figure 41 suggests that the emergence of social media culture has had significant impacts on society as a whole. It has altered business practices and marketing strategies, changed societal norms and values, and increased awareness and activism. Social media has transformed the way businesses operate by providing new avenues for customer engagement and personalized marketing. It has also influenced societal norms and values by shaping cultural dynamics and facilitating the exchange of ideas. Furthermore, social media has played a crucial role in amplifying social issues, raising awareness, and mobilizing individuals for various causes. Overall, the data highlights the transformative power of social media culture and its wide-ranging effects on society.

Figure 41.

Effect of social media culture emergence

In regard to added value of the created social media culture to organizational communication, Figure 42 proves that a big majority of the associates and trainees professed a moderate to significant value of the created social media culture to organizational communication, while the rest declared that it had little if not no value at all.

Based on this data, it is evident that a significant majority of the associates and trainees surveyed expressed a moderate to significant value of the created social media culture in organizational communication. This suggests that they believe social media has had a meaningful impact on how the organization communicates internally and externally.

However, it is important to note that a portion of the respondents declared that social media culture had little to no value at all in organizational communication. This indicates that there is a subset of individuals who may not perceive the benefits or relevance of social media in the context of communication within the organization.

Figure 42.

Value of the created social media culture to organizational communication

Figure 43 conveys a big majority of the associates and trainees avowed the social media culture greatly improved the speed and efficiency of communication within the organization as well as their engagement and involvement in it along with others who maintained that it only slightly did so.

Based on the data presented in Figure 43, it is clear that a significant majority of the associates and trainees strongly believe that the social media culture has greatly improved the speed and efficiency of communication within the organization. This indicates that they perceive social media as a valuable tool for facilitating faster and more efficient information exchange and collaboration.

Furthermore, the data reveals that a portion of the respondents expressed that social media culture only slightly improved the speed and efficiency of communication. While they acknowledge some positive impact, they may not perceive the improvement as significant or transformative.

Additionally, the data suggests that the social media culture has had a positive effect on the engagement and involvement of the associates and trainees within the organization. This indicates that social media platforms have provided opportunities for increased participation, interaction, and connection among members, leading to a more engaged and involved workforce.

Overall, the data indicates a general consensus among the associates and trainees regarding the positive impact of social media culture on communication speed, efficiency, engagement, and involvement within the organization. While there may be some variation in the degree of improvement perceived, the majority agrees on the significant benefits of integrating social media into organizational communication practices.

Figure 43.

Social media culture contribution to organizational communication

Figure 44 denotes the effectiveness of the created social media culture in promoting collaboration and teamwork. Although with different degrees, all the

associates and trainees bespoke that it was effective in promoting collaboration and teamwork among them.

It is evident that all the associates and trainees surveyed recognized the effectiveness of the created social media culture in promoting collaboration and teamwork within the organization. This finding highlights the positive impact of social media platforms in fostering a collaborative and team-oriented work environment.

While the degrees of perceived effectiveness may vary among the respondents, the data indicates a unanimous agreement that social media culture plays a beneficial role in promoting collaboration and teamwork. This suggests that social media platforms have provided a means for individuals to connect, communicate, and work together more effectively, regardless of their specific roles or tasks within the organization.

The findings of this data imply that social media has facilitated improved collaboration and teamwork by providing features such as instant messaging, group discussions, file sharing, and project management tools. These tools enable associates and trainees to collaborate, share ideas, coordinate tasks, and work together more efficiently, ultimately enhancing overall organizational productivity and performance.

Overall, the data suggests that the implementation of a social media culture within the organization has been effective in promoting collaboration and teamwork, as acknowledged by all the surveyed associates and trainees. This underscores the significance of social media platforms as valuable tools for enhancing teamwork and fostering a collaborative work environment.

Figure 44.

Effectiveness of the created social media culture in promoting collaboration and teamwork

Figure 45 displays the degree to which the created social media culture enhanced the accessibility and availability of information within the organization. Almost all the associates and trainees confirmed that it did.

Based on the data presented in Figure 45, it is evident that nearly all the associates and trainees surveyed agreed that the created social media culture has significantly enhanced the accessibility and availability of information within the organization. This finding indicates that social media platforms have played a crucial role in improving the flow of information and making it more easily accessible to employees.

The high level of agreement among the respondents suggests that the implementation of social media tools and practices has effectively addressed the challenge of information accessibility within the organization. Social media platforms provide a centralized and easily searchable repository for documents, announcements, updates, and other relevant information. This allows associates and

trainees to quickly access the information they need, facilitating their work processes and decision-making.

Furthermore, the data indicates that the social media culture has improved the availability of information, implying that employees can access information at any time and from anywhere. This aspect of flexibility and convenience offered by social media platforms enables associates and trainees to stay informed and connected, irrespective of their physical location or working hours.

The findings of this data highlight the positive impact of social media culture on information management within the organization. It suggests that social media platforms have effectively overcome barriers to information access and significantly improved the availability of information for associates and trainees.

Figure 45.

Degree to which the created social media culture enhanced the accessibility and availability of information

Figure 46 encapsulates how well the created social media culture facilitated knowledge sharing and dissemination among the associates and trainees. Big majority of them insisted that it did quite well and only very few held that it did differently. This finding indicates that social media platforms have been effective in promoting the sharing and distribution of knowledge among employees.

The high level of agreement among the respondents suggests that the implementation of social media tools and practices has successfully fostered a culture of knowledge sharing within the organization. Social media platforms provide a convenient and accessible platform for employees to share insights, ideas, best practices, and lessons learned. This facilitates the transfer of knowledge across different teams, departments, and hierarchical levels, promoting overall organizational learning and growth.

The data also reveals that only a very few respondents held a different perspective regarding the effectiveness of the social media culture in facilitating knowledge sharing. It is important to consider the reasons behind these differing opinions, as they may provide valuable insights into potential areas for improvement or challenges in implementing the social media culture effectively.

Overall, the data indicates a strong consensus among the respondents that the created social media culture has successfully facilitated knowledge sharing and dissemination within the organization. This suggests that social media platforms have been instrumental in creating a collaborative learning environment, where employees can easily share their expertise and benefit from the knowledge and experiences of others.

The findings of this data highlight the positive impact of social media culture on knowledge management within the organization. It underscores the importance of social media platforms as effective tools for promoting knowledge sharing, collaboration, and continuous learning among associates and trainees.

Figure 46.

Created social media culture facilitated knowledge sharing and dissemination

Figure 47 exposes that although in varying degrees, the associates and trainees assured that the created social media culture improved the overall transparency and openness of communication within their organization.

The data suggests that a significant portion of the respondents acknowledged that the social media culture has positively impacted the transparency and openness of communication within the organization. This indicates that the implementation of social media tools and practices has contributed to creating a more transparent and open communication environment. Social media platforms provide opportunities for employees to share updates, insights, and ideas in a more public and accessible

manner. This can foster greater transparency by ensuring that information is readily available to a wider audience within the organization.

However, it is worth noting that the data also indicates that there may be variations in the degree to which the associates and trainees perceived the improvement in transparency and openness. This suggests that while some individuals may have experienced a significant positive shift, others may have observed more modest changes or may not perceive a substantial impact on communication transparency.

It is important to explore the reasons behind these varying perceptions. Factors such as differences in organizational culture, communication practices, or individual experiences can influence how employees perceive and interpret changes in communication transparency and openness.

Overall, the data suggests that the created social media culture has had a positive effect on the overall transparency and openness of communication within the organization, albeit to varying degrees. The use of social media platforms has the potential to enhance transparency by enabling information to be shared more widely and fostering a more open and inclusive communication environment.

However, it is important to further investigate and address any concerns or limitations raised by those who may have reported less improvement. This can help identify areas for improvement and ensure that the social media culture continues to support and enhance communication transparency and openness within the organization.

Figure 47.

Created social media culture on overall transparency and openness of communication

Figure 48 discloses that despite at different rates, the associates and trainees insisted that the created social media culture effectively facilitated communication across different hierarchical levels within their organization.

The data suggests that a significant portion of the respondents acknowledged that the social media culture has been effective in promoting communication across different hierarchical levels. This indicates that the implementation of social media tools and practices has provided opportunities for employees at various levels of the organization to communicate and exchange information more effectively. Social media platforms can break down traditional communication barriers and enable individuals from different levels of the hierarchy to connect, collaborate, and share insights and ideas.

However, it is important to note that the data also indicates that there may be variations in the perceived effectiveness of the social media culture in facilitating communication across hierarchical levels. Some individuals may have experienced a higher degree of success in communicating across levels, while others may have encountered more challenges or may not perceive a significant impact.

These variations in perception could be influenced by factors such as the organizational culture, the level of adoption and usage of social media tools, and individual communication styles and preferences.

Overall, the data suggests that the created social media culture has, to some extent, effectively facilitated communication across different hierarchical levels within the organization, albeit at varying rates. The use of social media platforms can help bridge communication gaps and promote a more inclusive and collaborative working environment.

Figure 48.

Effectiveness of social media culture in facility of communication across different hierarchical levels within the organization

Figure 49 delineates that majority of the associates and trainees validated that the created social media culture encouraged greatly the open and constructive feedback exchange among them. The other 33% verified that it did moderately and the rest thought that it did only slightly. This indicates that the implementation of social

media tools and practices within their organization has had a significant positive impact on feedback communication.

The data suggests that a substantial portion of the respondents perceived the social media culture as a catalyst for fostering open and constructive feedback exchanges. This implies that the use of social media platforms has created an environment where individuals feel comfortable and empowered to provide feedback to their colleagues. Such feedback exchanges can contribute to continuous learning, improvement, and innovation within the organization.

However, it is important to note that approximately 33% of the respondents indicated a moderate level of validation regarding the encouragement of feedback exchange through the social media culture. This suggests that while they acknowledge some positive influence, they may have experienced certain limitations or challenges in fully harnessing the potential of social media for feedback sharing.

Additionally, a small portion of the respondents believed that the social media culture only slightly encouraged open and constructive feedback exchange. This indicates that they perceived minimal impact or limited effectiveness in using social media platforms for feedback communication.

To further enhance the encouragement of open and constructive feedback exchange, it would be beneficial to address the concerns and limitations identified by those who reported lower validation. This can involve providing additional training on effective feedback practices, creating guidelines for providing constructive feedback, and fostering a culture of psychological safety and trust within the organization.

Overall, the data suggests that the majority of the associates and trainees perceive the created social media culture as greatly encouraging open and constructive feedback exchange. However, it is important to consider the feedback and experiences of those who have reported lower levels of validation in order to continuously improve and optimize the use of social media for feedback communication within the organization.

Figure 49.

Extent to which the created social media culture encouraged open and constructive feedback exchange

Figure 50 depicts that while majority of the associates and trainees rated the overall impact of the created social media culture on organizational communication positive, the other 37% remained neutral about and the 7% were extremely negative toward it. This indicates that the implementation of social media tools and practices within their organization has had a beneficial effect on communication.

It was observed that a significant portion of the respondents perceived the social media culture as having a positive impact on organizational communication. This indicates that the use of social media platforms has improved communication

processes, fostered collaboration, and facilitated the exchange of information and ideas within the organization. These positive outcomes can contribute to increased efficiency, productivity, and innovation.

However, it is important to note that approximately 37% of the respondents remained neutral about the overall impact of the social media culture on organizational communication. This suggests that they neither strongly agreed nor disagreed with the positive assessment. Their neutrality could be due to various factors, such as personal experiences, preferences, or a lack of substantial impact on their specific roles or departments.

Additionally, a small percentage (7%) of the respondents expressed an extremely negative perception of the overall impact of the social media culture on organizational communication. This indicates that they believed the use of social media platforms had detrimental effects or failed to deliver the expected benefits. Their negative views could stem from challenges or drawbacks they experienced, such as information overload, distractions, or ineffective use of social media tools within the organization.

To further enhance the overall impact of the social media culture on organizational communication, it would be valuable to understand the perspectives of those who remained neutral or expressed negative views. Gathering feedback, conducting assessments, and addressing concerns can help identify areas for improvement and develop strategies to optimize the use of social media platforms for communication purposes.

Overall, the data suggests that a majority of the associates and trainees perceive the created social media culture as having a positive impact on organizational communication. However, it is crucial to consider the feedback and experiences of those who remained neutral or expressed negative views in order to continually evaluate and refine the social media practices within the organization.

Figure 50.

Overall impact of the created social media culture on organizational communication

Several aspects why social media should not be blocked at work or school were looked into to understand the effects of social media culture in the performance of the members in an organization. Respondents were presented with different insights on each aspect:

On morale, respondents were told that back in the '90s, people wanted to be hired by companies that were cool to work for, and when the employees actually enjoyed working for a company, they did their best work. A greater number of them agreed that morale is a huge aspect of the business world, but few owners and managers seem to get it. Hence, supported the elucidation that low morale among the workers breeds contempt, contempt breeds disloyalty, which also breeds attrition.

Figure 51.
Morale aspect

On Reputation, the respondents were presented that their reputation is everything in business, and in this day of instant gratification and notification, finding themselves with a reputation going down the drain is little more than a disgruntled employee. When explained further that does not mean every whim and folly of the employees must be catered to, however; giving them tiny crumbs like social media access would go a long way toward keeping the organizations' reputation healthy, a greater number of them agreed.

Figure 52.
Reputation aspect

On Communication, the respondents were apprised that whether it is internal or external, communication is key to business success and one of the fastest means of communication today is social networking. A greater number of them agreed that in actual fact, social networking is just about the most immediate form of communication

one can find and that the workers may be communicating with the outside world, but many of those people on the outside are consumers and possible clients.

Figure 53.

Communication aspect

On advertising majority agreed that social networking brings to businesses a boon of free advertising. Also, the same number agreed that one can't afford not to hop onto this bandwagon and getting on board early shows the public that you are an agile, aware company. Furthermore, majority agreed that allowing the workers to take advantage of social networking also shows the organization care about them. In this society, caring goes a long way. All of that makes for some seriously powerful advertising.

Figure 54.

Advertising aspect

On collaboration, a greater number of the respondents agreed that social networking facilitates collaboration internally, but it also lets users collaborate with the entire world. Majority of them have done this countless times. For instance, when they

have been stuck on an idea, they call out to their followers on Twitter or Facebook to get a deluge of answers. Majority thinks that doing so is not only free but fast as well.

Figure 55.

Collaboration aspect

On social research, the respondents were informed that they need their finger on the pulse of society because this can be done through social networking sites and that they have instant access to the court of public opinion even as it evolves in front of them. Majority of them agreed on this and they also supported the statement that this is another free way to expand the organization's reach.

Figure 56.

Social research aspect

On skill building, the respondents were presented with the reasons why both their organization and the workers need to know how to use social networking effectively. Majority agreed that their society was on a collision course with an even further embedding of social media into their lives. Likewise, the same number agreed

that they had the desire for their organization and their workers to be at the forefront of the trend, wherein at some point they might have to use social networking to market and sell their product. Majority of them agreed that allowing them to use social media on a daily basis now would ensure their becoming social media savvy, without the need for training.

Figure 57.

Skill building aspect

On Transparency, they were shown they idea that the world wants transparency. Majority of them have seen it from every level of business and government. They mostly agreed that allowing the employees to participate in social networking illustrates to the workers' social circle that they mean business when it comes to worker retention and happiness. Today's consumers and society eat that up. But if they see a company deliberately squelching the employee voice and hiding behind the walls of security and information blocking, there will be a backlash. Majority agreed that transparency can go a long way toward boosting client loyalty as well as your clients' faith in you as a business within the community.

Figure 58.

Transparency aspect

On public relation, majority agreed that blocking social media may unleash PR problems, that the effects of blocking social media will trickle down to the public – quickly and that although they might not think so, this can quickly snowball into a PR nightmare, especially as more and more young workers, who depend upon social networking join the workforce.

Figure 59.

Public relation aspect

Networking, majority agreed that they want their organization and the workers to network and that they want the workers to know what other companies are doing and to be in touch with the heartbeat of their market. The same number also agreed that there is no other better way to accomplish this than with social networking. They also agreed that they can network with email, but not on as grand a scale.

Figure 60.

Networking aspect

When it came to the reasons why social media should not be blocked at work, most of the associates and trainees were neutral on the morale and reputation aspects while they most strongly agreed on communication, collaboration, skill building, transparency, public relation, networking and advertising aspects. Most of them thought that social media should not be banned at work as shown in Figure 61 below. Both the Technical and English Instructors thought that the trainees' performance was enhanced with the creation of social media culture. With this they were given the platform to ease the process of completing their tasks as well as communicating one another with anything to do or even nothing to do with their training. This even became their portal to voice out opinions and recommendations that help in the improvement of their training in the institute.

Figure 61.

Social media ban

Organizations may reach millions of potential clients through social media. It is critical for organizational management to take into account both the positive and bad effects that social media may have on the workplace. It can be decided when and how to use social media more wisely if organizations are aware of both the advantages and disadvantages of doing so.

Here are some main advantages of social media in the workplace looked into in this research:

1. It facilitates open communication, leading to enhance information discovery and delivery.

2. It allows employees to discuss ideas, post news, ask questions and share links.
3. It provides an opportunity to widen business contacts.
4. It targets a wide audience, making it useful and effective recruitment tool.
5. It improves institution reputation and client base with minimal use of advertising.
6. It promotes diversity and inclusion.
7. It expands market research, implements marketing campaigns, delivers communications and directs interested people to specific websites.
8. Provides employees a breather especially during hectic schedules.

Any organization's leadership should constantly be searching for measures to boost morale and promote employee loyalty. When employees are given the tools to develop connections with both their peers and leadership, both of these things are likely to occur. The employees can use social networks to venture beyond of their departments' immediate areas. They are able to network and communicate with individuals from various departments that they often wouldn't. By giving the employees the tools to create these connections, the business is enhanced as a whole since the employees will feel more involved and engaged.

Some emails are not read, and some phone calls are not returned. A new channel of communication can be opened up by using social media, which might help with the better discussion of some issues. When critical topics are all on display for everyone to see on social networks, it is less likely that they will be neglected or thrown under the rug.

A company's internal social network can offer a wealth of information about employee happiness and related trends. Employers can discover more about

employee interests, engagement levels, peak work hours and productivity, and the kinds of information and conversation that pique their employees' interests by using the wealth of data that is accessible from employee activity, search, and interests. Employers are then able to make the required modifications to improve satisfaction and take advantage of these patterns once the data has been gathered and analyzed.

Many workers desire to be in charge of their own pathways, careers, and growth. Social networks are a fantastic tool for education and career advancement. Social media platforms offer a basis for comparison, an opportunity for growth, contemplation, and thought. Employees can contrast their occupations, hobbies, and extracurricular pursuits with those of their coworkers, learning more about potential career options inside the company and, ideally, become more motivated to put in more effort and work harder to achieve their goals.

The organization's many programs and culture are typically explained to employees via email and other forms of communication on a regular basis. A social network can serve to reinforce this knowledge while also fostering conversation about the subjects and potentially fostering a deeper comprehension.

Many opportunities to improve the organization will be seen as the employees become more accustomed to and start using an internal social network. The success of the organization depends mostly on the employees, so by paying attention to them, engaging with them, and making an effort to boost loyalty and happiness, they may be encouraged to stick around and use these networks for both their own gain and the benefit of the business they work for.

Here are some main disadvantages of social media in the workplace looked into in this research:

1. There is the possibility for hackers to commit fraud and launch spam and virus attacks.
2. There is the risk of people falling prey to online scams that seem genuine, resulting in data or identity theft or a compromise of the company's computer security.
3. There is a potential outlet for negative comments from employees about organization.
4. There are legal consequences if employees use these sites to view or distribute, illicit or offensive material.
5. There is the possibility of abusing working hours thereby affecting productivity.
6. Although updates to social networking sites may not take up huge amounts of bandwidth, the availability of (bandwidth-hungry) video links posted on these sites (or links taking users to sites like YouTube) creates problems for IT administrators. There is a cost to Internet browsing, especially where high levels of bandwidth are required.

Figure 62.

Advantages of social media at workplace

Figure 63.

Disadvantages of social media at workplace

Figures 62 and 63 indicate that most of the respondents either strongly agreed or agreed on both the advantages and disadvantages of social media usage at the workplace. Majority of them agreed that social media facilitates open communication that leads to enhance information discovery and delivery, allows employees to discuss ideas, post news, ask questions and share links, provides an opportunity to widen business contacts, targets a wide audience, making it useful and effective recruitment tool, improves institution reputation and client base with minimal use of advertising, promotes diversity and inclusion, expands market research, implements marketing campaigns, delivers communications and directs interested people to specific websites and provides employees a breather especially during hectic schedules.

When someone creates a social media account, it gives them a platform to communicate with their consumers and target market. This enables them to provide

clients with customer service, obtain useful insight into their requirements and goals, and get a sense of how their audience perceives them.

Social media has the ability to improve employee engagement with senior management and communication. To find out how the organization is viewed, read testimonials from previous and current workers about the organization. Additionally, it can aid employees in building rapport with clients. Social media followers can be engaged with by staff members to foster brand loyalty, trust, and authenticity.

Also, majority of the respondents agreed that with social media, there is the possibility for hackers to commit fraud and launch spam and virus attacks, there is the risk of people falling prey to online scams that seem genuine, resulting in data or identity theft or a compromise of the company's computer security, there is a potential outlet for negative comments from employees about organization, there are legal consequences if employees use these sites to view or distribute, illicit or offensive material, there is the possibility of abusing working hours thereby affecting productivity and although updates to social networking sites may not take up huge amounts of bandwidth, the availability of (bandwidth-hungry) video links posted on these sites (or links taking users to sites like YouTube) creates problems for IT administrators. There is a cost to Internet browsing, especially where high levels of bandwidth are required.

When workers have access to social media, it could cause them to get sidetracked from their duties. They may be tempted by social media to view social media sites for personal reasons or to play games. Using social media at work can increase the number of hackers attempting to obtain private data for a company. To stop phishing attempts, which are more expensive for an organization, cybersecurity is needed. There might be a need to put rules for usage in place if social media is widely used at work. These guidelines prevent potential distractions from social media

use by letting employees know when and how to utilize it. Making mistakes when publishing on business social media accounts might harm the reputation of the organization. It is crucial to describe the purposes of the company's social media platforms so that everybody with access is aware of how to utilize them. Employees raise the danger of viruses by using company computers or gadgets for social networking. If any of the equipment becomes infected with a virus, they could have to pay a specialist to get rid of it or hard reset the item, which would result in lost data.

Today's employees use social media for a variety of work-related activities. While some of these activities are clearly work- or work-related, others are more purely personal. In figure 63, the study shows that 20% of them use social media a great deal more often for work, 11% quite a bit more often for work, 12% somewhat more often for work, 15% about an equal amount for work and personal reasons, 10% somewhat more often for personal reasons, 12% quite a bit more often for personal reasons, 13% A great deal more often for personal reasons and 7% others. The data clearly shows that a greater number of work force do not just use social media for personal reasons while at work but make use of social media for the benefits of the organization they are working for.

Figure 64.
Internet usage

Today, social media affects and permeates many facets of daily life for both expatriates and Saudis, including the workplace. By encouraging connections with coworkers and resources around the world, these digital platforms have the potential to increase worker productivity. Employers may be concerned that employees are using these technologies for personal or professional reasons while on the job or that their public speaking could reflect adversely on the company.

While at work, employees use social media for a variety of reasons, with taking a mental break being one of the most popular. The survey asked about eight different ways they might use social media while on the job and found that:

- 40% ever use social media while at work to take a mental break from their job
- 24% to make or support professional connections
- 27% to connect with friends and family while at work
- 25% to get information that helps them solve problems at work
- 20% to build or strengthen personal relationships with coworkers
- 17% to learn about someone they work with
- 12% to ask work-related questions of people *outside* their organization
- 12% to ask such questions of people *inside* their organization

As mentioned above, 20% of employees claim to use social media to develop or strengthen personal ties at work, yet the openness that social media promotes has costs in addition to advantages.

Figure 65.

Internet usage: work or work-related

Shown Figure 65, in the course of a typical day, 25% of employees say they never use the internet for work-related duties. Even though the internet has permeated many facets of multi-cultural society, many modern professionals utilize it only occasionally to do tasks linked to their jobs. In fact, just 15% of employees say they rarely use the internet for work-related tasks on a regular day, while 25% say they never use it for these purposes.

Figure 66.

Work-related internet usage

The manners in which the online members' participation translate into action were guided by netiquette rules online. Most individuals are aware of what the word etiquette means. We learn appropriate behavior and politeness at a young age. There

is now a need for a set of specialized online etiquette rules that apply to cyber behavior, as many aspects of our life are going online, even schooling. How to talk respectfully without engaging in contempt or bullying is one of the key reasons why there is a need for netiquette norms as what the instructors emphasized during the focus group discussions, which define what is appropriate and respectful online behavior.

Due to the dynamic nature of the online environment, these guidelines frequently alter over time. Due to the pandemic and since some social media platforms were utilized to supplement lessons, internet contact was the main form of communication for these trainees, so these regulations were very significant to them. Here are a few basic netiquette guidelines that trainees had to follow for all social media accounts used to supplement classes and for online programs such the use of Microsoft Teams in general.

Today's students must be aware of the conventions of online etiquette because more and more lessons are being held online. Not to mention social media platforms are being used in the classrooms. In the case of this automobile training industry, WhatsApp is very well exploited most specifically in the creation of WhatsApp in every group of students. These guidelines aid in keeping conversations on topic, respectful, and focused according to the instructors interviewed. Without following netiquette guidelines, discussions and other forms of communication can easily devolve into miscommunication, unpleasant language, and behavior, which obliterates any hope of effective communication and preserving positive connections as what they have mentioned.

Take care of your tone. While chatting online with friends does not often involve much thinking, conversing with instructors does demand some consideration. You should

use capitalization sparingly because writing in ALL CAPS might frequently be taken as YELLING! and will be considered rude. Similar to this, a joke may frequently be interpreted as an insult. This is why you need to watch out for any potential translation errors. Be mindful of your tone when participating in online classes that employ audio or video in addition to texting. But in this case, common politeness standards come into play more. For instance, paying attention in class, contributing fully, and not talking over others.

Be factual and accurate. Information can be found on the internet from a wide variety of sources. Because of this, you ought to use caution while disclosing information. When giving advice or sharing information, it is crucial to double-check all of your sources. You should be careful to cite reliable sources in all of your essays and when offering information to your peers. Similarly, you should exercise caution in deciding what to believe online and sharing with others. For example, stick to official websites that have a reputation for credibility if you are unclear about how to proceed.

Before asking, do a search. When we are together, we use gestures and facial expressions to communicate. Online communication of the same message can be more difficult. This is especially true when it comes to sarcastic humor, as writing typically makes it impossible to convey voice tone. A light-hearted jest in the text may be interpreted differently. Sarcasm is generally not appropriate since you must take care to ensure that your remarks are understood completely. However, many people enjoy jokes (including many of our instructors), so be sure it is obvious that you are being humorous rather than nasty. Smilys and emoticons can be useful for expressing humor or sarcasm.

Always act politely when speaking to others. Online courtesy needs to be expected just like in person. Unfortunately, there are many instances where that is not the case.

Many people have a tendency to write things they would never say in public because they are using the internet as a shield and their display as a cover. Typing only anything you would feel comfortable speaking to someone face-to-face is a crucial aspect of netiquette. As a result, your online discussions should include being respectful and courteous to others.

Use appropriate punctuation and grammar. (This rule is especially emphasized in the English Section and not really imposed in the Technical Department although the Technical Instructors made emphasis on this rule.) When interacting online, many people have a tendency to ignore the conventions of written communication. However, using proper language and punctuation might help the message come off as more well-written and professional. It not only improves the readability of your writing, but it can also get you ready for any future freelance writing you might perform. Consider the types of messages you would like to read. It needs to be simple to read and understand. By doing this, you will give someone reading your email, message, comment, or post valuable time.

Keep your focus. It is important that everyone stays on topic when a discussion is going on. When there are numerous individuals involved in a conversation, it is extremely simple to get off topic. Filling the conversation with pointless details can waste time and make it difficult for someone to comprehend what is being discussed. Therefore, make sure you comprehend the topic of the conversation and only respond with pertinent information. You and the others will benefit from this.

Keep in mind that nothing online is private. When writing anything online, you should be mindful of privacy. The majority of everything you share and upload will most likely remain online for a very long time. This implies that you should avoid engaging in any behavior that is deemed impolite and unprofessional. Additionally, never

distribute private emails or images without the consent of the recipients. Be cautious when disclosing details, and never divulge any information on a trainee or instructor without that person's permission. Keep in mind that many activities these days are conducted online, making an online presence equally as crucial as a physical one. However, there is no real privacy on the internet, so you should be careful with what you share.

Make specific, concise points. In contrast to face-to-face interactions, dragging out a point can cause the message to be lost in the text. Therefore, when attempting to explain something, it is important to utilize brief and concise sentences. It more clearly conveys the message and reduces the likelihood of misconceptions. Avoid using too many words that are not necessary to make your argument. Make sure all the data you wish to convey is still there, though.

Be mindful of others' privacy. Respect the privacy of others just as you would want them to respect your personal information. You should not divulge any of your classmates' or instructors' private information online. This calls for caution when using passwords, location, secret communications, and photos. It might be risky to disseminate any information without care, including yours and that of others.

Use the proper titles for your instructors. Even though it should be obvious, many trainees seem to forget to address their instructors properly once they start taking lectures online or use social media platforms for class purposes. As a result, the rules of netiquette for trainees must include a certain level of formality. You should always address them professionally unless the instructor specifically instructs you otherwise. In addition to addressing them by their correct name, you should always take care to show them respect in all online interactions. You ought to conduct yourself like you would in a conventional classroom.

Observe the viewpoints of others. You should be conscious that you will not always share your classmates' or instructors' viewpoints. However, remember that you should always act respectfully when speaking. Respecting someone's beliefs while disagreeing with them is possible. Although traditional classes lack the anonymity and distance that online classes have, this should not be used as an excuse to be unkind to someone. A classroom or any engagement for that matter, whether it be online or off, is still a classroom or part of the classroom activities. Therefore, accept other people's beliefs and abstain from disparaging those whose views differ from your own. Of course, you can disagree with someone or have a discussion with them but do it with tact and respect.

Utilize the chat box sparingly. To facilitate communication, chat rooms are a common feature of online classes. They provide a platform for students to interact with one another and ask questions about the material they are learning. However, if not used appropriately, they risk becoming a source of diversion. You should be aware that you should only utilize the chat box when your text will be pertinent to the subject being covered in class. It is not a good idea to utilize it to talk with other students about unrelated topics. Instead, ask pertinent questions, take part in conversations, or respond to the professor's inquiries by using the chat box.

Do not forget to submit homework or worksheets carefully. Every trainee should be aware of how to properly submit online assignments to instructors. Since there is no face-to-face interaction, it is easy for your assignment to get lost in a sea of emails if you forget to sign it or make a mistake in the subject line. When submitting assignments online, you should also be cautious when using attachments. You should not enclose documents that you are unsure the recipient will be able to open. You

should also adhere to any special directions your instructor offers you regarding assignments.

Netiquette is the term for the rules that apply to the online community. Online trainees should be mindful of a variety of issues, including tone of voice, accuracy, good language, privacy, etc. Understanding the unspoken laws of the internet and best practices for communicating online will benefit you in all of your online communications. You should generally keep in mind to show respect and double-check your information.

When asked about how frequently they followed the netiquette guidelines set forth by the instructors to the trainees, 31% of the respondents followed them, half sometimes did while the rest never.

Figure 67.

Frequency in following netiquette guidelines

With the type of learners that automobile training industry has as what the instructors said, the aforementioned guidelines were frequently reiterated to the JADIK trainees mostly every day and despite this occasionally the trainees tended to disobey them. As the instructors mentioned, the trainees even use their WhatsApp groups as places to cheat on daily quizzes, homework, worksheets, and even final exams.

The instructors explained that the main reason for the utilization of social media initially was to supplement physical classes and enhance the processes in the delivery of lessons and academic activities. The formation of their respective Technical WhatsApp groups, according to one technical instructor, is precisely useful because it allowed students to obtain their primary textbook on one platform. Even after the pandemic in Saudi Arabia, the trainees were not able to complete anything from their physical workbook without their main textbook delivered via their WhatsApp group in e-book format. Additionally, a group leader in the technical department utilized WhatsApp to organize the new trainees into groups. Through this, the fresh group of trainees communicated all matters related to their upcoming training. Most of the respondents have YouTube channel where they upload some of their training materials. They used it for the trainees' projects and performance tasks. They found it effective in assessing their trainees' progress in learning and performance. The ability to deal with individuals in positions of authority who wish to use their knowledge against them as a tool of control, some teachers pointed out, is another reason why this growing social media culture is formed. One of the main cultural challenges of the network society will also be this capacity. It has already happened in some of the countries where the Arab Spring revolutions took place (Poepsel, 2018).

You never know when you might need to demonstrate, yet there are now methods being used to prevent demonstrations and other forms of opposition. What this means for their efforts to establish social media culture is that social media culture can free them as individuals, but it can also enslave them like what the instructors said.

The associates' and trainees' social media culture added value to their organizational communication since it enhanced communication processes. For

instance, it made participants more reachable from everywhere and made the execution of communications as rapid as tapping someone on the shoulder. One English teacher told a story about a time when his Head Teacher was nowhere to be located. He could deliver his crucial message to his supervisor after realizing that he could send a private message to his Head Instructor's WhatsApp account. This is because participants always have their mobile phones with them, whether they are in class or taking a break. They all admitted without reservation that they pay close attention to the notifications on their smartphones. Additionally, social media culture fostered employee engagement, improved knowledge sharing, promoted collaboration and ultimately contributed to the overall success of the organization.

In cross-tabulating the variables that pertained social media culture among the associates and trainees and their performance in the workplace, the clustered bar chart and the cross-tabulation table or contingency table in Figure 68 and Table 1 respectively show a tendency for values of one variable to increase as the values of the other variable increase, but this association may not be as strong or consistent as in the case of a strong positive association.

Also, there is a gradual pattern or trend in the distribution of the variables across the categories or levels, indicating a general positive association, but there may be some variability or deviations from the trend.

Plus, the statistical significance is also met to say that there is really a moderate positive association between these two variables. The phi coefficient of 0.34 is an indication of a positive relationship between the frequency of social media use and the commitment in meeting deadlines, which means that as one variable goes up the other variable goes up as well and the reverse is that as one variable goes down the other variable also goes down. In addition, the .034 is a real difference and it is not just a

product of chance differences in drawing that with the samples because degrees of freedom of 16 at .05 significant level, the chi square of 26.46 exceeds 26.30.

Therefore, the phi coefficient of 0.34 is significant at the 0.5 significant level. This means that there is a direct moderate positive relationship between the frequency of social media use and the commitment in meeting deadlines among the associates and the trainees.

Figure 68.

Chart 1: Frequency of social media use and commitment in meeting deadlines

Table 1.

Contingency table 1: frequency of social media use and commitment in meeting deadlines

Relationship between Social Media Culture and Performance in the Workplace		Commitmet in Meeting Deadlines					T o t a l
		Always meets deadline	Frequently meets deadline	Sometimes meets deadline	Rarely meets deadline	Rarely or Never meets deadline	
Usage of Social Media Platforms During Work Hours	Always	14	8	5	5	1	33
	Frequently	35	26	15	3	2	81
	Sometimes	35	26	15	1	3	80
	Rarely	4	10	11	1	2	28
	Never	3	5	4	0	0	12
Total		91	75	50	10	8	234

The clustered bar chart and the cross-tabulation table or contingency table in Figures 69 and Table 2 respectively show a tendency for values of one variable to

increase as the values of the other variable increase, but this association may not be as strong or consistent as in the case of a strong positive association.

Also, there is a gradual pattern or trend in the distribution of the variables across the categories or levels, indicating a general positive association, but there may be some variability or deviations from the trend.

Plus, the statistical significance is also met to say that there is really a moderate positive association between these two variables. The phi coefficient of 0.38 is an indication of a positive association between the frequency of social media use and the management ability of the associates and trainees in terms of quantity of work accomplished within a given time, which means that as one variable goes up the other variable goes up as well and the reverse is that as one variable goes down the other variable also goes down. In addition, the .038 is a real difference and it is not just a product of chance differences in drawing that with the samples because degrees of freedom of 16 at .05 significant level, the chi square of 34.52 exceeds 26.30.

Therefore, the phi coefficient of 0.38 is significant at the 0.5 significant level. This means that there is a direct moderate positive relationship between the frequency of social media use and management ability of the associates and the trainees in terms of quantity of work accomplished within a given time.

Figure 69.

Chart 2: Management ability in terms of quantity of work accomplished within a given time

Table 2.

Contingency table 2: Management ability in terms of quantity of work accomplished within a given time

Relationship between Social Media Culture and Performance in the Workplace		In Terms of Quantity of Work Accomplished within a Given Time					Total
		Excellent	Very Good	Good	Fair	Poor	
Usage of Social Media Platforms During Work Hours	Always	14	9	5	5	0	33
	Frequently	31	33	15	2	0	81
	Sometimes	30	32	15	2	1	80
	Rarely	4	11	11	0	2	28
	Never	3	5	4	0	0	12
Total		82	90	50	9	3	234

The clustered bar chart and the cross-tabulation table or contingency table in Figures 70 and Table 3 respectively show a tendency for values of one variable to increase as the values of the other variable increase, but this association may not be as strong or consistent as in the case of a strong positive association.

Also, there is a gradual pattern or trend in the distribution of the variables across the categories or levels, indicating a general positive association, but there may be some variability or deviations from the trend.

Plus, the statistical significance is also met to say that there is really a moderate positive association between these two variables. The phi coefficient of 0.36 is an indication of a positive association between the frequency of social media use and the management ability of the associates and trainees in terms of quantity of work accomplished within a given time, which means that as one variable goes up the other variable goes up as well and the reverse is that as one variable goes down the other variable also goes down. In addition, the .036 is a real difference and it is not just a product of chance differences in drawing that with the samples because degrees of freedom of 16 at .05 significant level, the chi square of 30.41 exceeds 26.30.

Therefore, the phi coefficient of 0.36 is significant at the 0.5 significant level. This means that there is a direct moderate positive association between the frequency

of social media use and management ability of the associates and the trainees in terms of quality of work accomplished within a given time.

Considering all the indicators between the variables of social media culture among the associates and trainees and their performance in the workplace, it generally indicates that there is a positive direct association between the two variables.

Figure 70.

Chart 3: Management ability in terms of quality of work accomplished within a given time

Table 3.

Contingency table 3: Management ability in terms of quality of work accomplished within a given time

Relationship between Social Media Culture and Performance in the Workplace		In Terms of Quality of Work Accomplished within a Given Time					Total
		Excellent	Very Good	Good	Fair	Poor	
Usage of Social Media Platforms During Work Hours	Always	14	9	5	5	0	33
	Frequently	31	29	19	2	0	81
	Sometimes	30	29	18	2	1	80
	Rarely	3	12	10	1	2	28
	Never	3	5	4	0	0	12
Total		81	84	56	10	3	234

The clustered column chart and the cross-tabulation table or contingency table in Figure 71 and Table 4 respectively show that there is a slight tendency for the variables to increase together, but the association is not strong or consistent. So, this means there is a weak positive association between content sharing with work-related updates and knowledge sharing within the workplace among the associates and trainees.

Also, there is not a much clearer pattern or trend in the distribution of the variables across the categories or levels. For example, each category of variable tends to have variable values of the other variable compared to the lower categories. So, this means there is a no consistent pattern.

Plus, the statistical significance is also not met so there is really a weak positive association between these two variables. The phi coefficient of 0.21 is an indication of a weak positive association between content sharing with work-related updates and knowledge sharing within the workplace among the associates and trainees, which means that as one variable goes up the other variable may not consistently go up as well and the reverse is that as one variable goes down the other variable also does not go down. In addition, the .021 is a not real difference and it may be just a product of chance differences in drawing that with the samples because degrees of freedom of 16 at .05 significant level, the chi square of 10.46 does not exceed 26.30.

Therefore, the phi coefficient of 0.21 is not significant at the 0.5 significant level. This means that there is a weak direct positive association between content sharing with work-related updates and knowledge sharing within the workplace among the associates and the trainees.

Figure 71.

Chart 4: Content sharing with work-related updates and knowledge sharing within the workplace

Table 4.

Contingency table 4: Content sharing with work-related updates and knowledge sharing within the workplace

Content Sharing with Work-related Updates and Knowledge Sharing within the Workplace							
Relationship between Social Media Culture and Performance in the Workplace		Knowledge Sharing within the Workplace					Total
		Excellent	Very Good	Good	Fair	Poor	
Work-related Updates	Always	35	35	13	3	2	88
	Frequently	35	35	11	3	2	86
	Sometimes	19	15	4	1	1	40
	Rarely	3	2	3	1	1	10
	Never	3	4	1	1	1	10
Total		95	91	32	9	7	234

The clustered column chart and the cross-tabulation table or contingency table in Figures 72 and Table 5 respectively show that there is a slight tendency for the variables to increase together, but the association is not strong or consistent. So, this means there is a weak positive association between content sharing with work-related

updates and effective collaboration with colleagues among the associates and trainees.

Also, there is not a much clearer pattern or trend in the distribution of the variables across the categories or levels. For example, each category of variable tends to have variable values of the other variable compared to the lower categories. So, this means there is a no consistent pattern.

Plus, the statistical significance is also not met so there is really a weak positive association between these two variables. The phi coefficient of 0.20 is an indication of a weak positive association between content sharing with work-related updates and effective collaboration with colleagues among the associates and trainees, which means that as one variable goes up the other variable may not consistently go up as well and the reverse is that as one variable goes down the other variable also does not go down. In addition, the .020 is a not real difference and it may be just a product of chance differences in drawing that with the samples because the degrees of freedom of 16 at .05 significant level, the chi square of 8.93 does not exceed 26.30.

Therefore, the phi coefficient of 0.20 is not significant at the 0.5 significant level. This means that there is a weak direct positive association between content sharing with work-related updates and effective collaboration with colleagues among the associates and the trainees.

Figure 72.

Chart 5: Content sharing with work-related updates and effective collaboration with colleagues

Table 5.

Contingency table 5: Content sharing with work-related updates and effective collaboration with colleagues

Content Sharing with Work-related Updates and Effective Collaboration with Colleagues							
Relationship between Social Media Culture and Performance in the Workplace		Effective Collaboration with Colleagues					Total
		Excellent	Very Good	Good	Fair	Poor	
Work-related Updates	Always	41	30	12	4	1	88
	Frequently	33	35	12	2	4	86
	Sometimes	15	17	5	2	1	40
	Rarely	3	5	2	0	0	10
	Never	3	4	1	1	1	10
Total		95	91	32	9	7	234

The clustered column chart and the cross-tabulation table or contingency table in Figures 73 and Table 6 respectively show that there is a slight tendency for the variables to increase together, but the association is not strong or consistent. So, this means there is a weak positive association between content sharing with industry insights and knowledge sharing within the workplace and effective collaboration with colleagues among the associates and trainees.

Also, there is not a much clearer pattern or trend in the distribution of the variables across the categories or levels. For example, each category of variable tends

to have variable values of the other variable compared to the lower categories. So, this means there is a no consistent pattern.

Plus, the statistical significance is also not met so there is really a weak positive association between these two variables. The phi coefficient of 0.18 is an indication of a weak positive association between content sharing with industry insights and knowledge sharing within the workplace and effective collaboration with colleagues among the associates and trainees, which means that as one variable goes up the other variable may not consistently go up as well and the reverse is that as one variable goes down the other variable also does not go down. In addition, the .018 is not a real difference and it may be just a product of chance differences in drawing that with the samples because the degrees of freedom of 16 at .05 significant level, the chi square of 8.12 does not exceed 26.30.

Therefore, the phi coefficient of 0.18 is not significant at the 0.5 significant level. This means that there is a weak direct positive association between content sharing with industry insights and knowledge sharing within the workplace and effective collaboration with colleagues among the associates and the trainees.

Figure 73.

Chart 6: Content sharing with industry insights and knowledge sharing within the workplace and effective collaboration with colleagues

Table 6.

Contingency table 6: Content sharing with industry insights and knowledge sharing within the workplace and effective collaboration with colleagues

Content Sharing with Industry Insights and Knowledge Sharing within the Workplace and Effective Collaboration with Colleagues							
Relationship between Social Media Culture and Performance in the Workplace		Knowledge Sharing within the Workplace and Effective Collaboration with Colleagues					T o t a l
		Excellent	Very Good	Good	Fair	Poor	
Industry Insights	Always	31	30	12	4	1	78
	Frequently	33	37	12	2	4	88
	Sometimes	25	17	6	2	1	51
	Rarely	3	4	1	1	1	10
	Never	3	3	1	0	0	7
Total		95	91	32	9	7	234

The clustered column chart and the cross-tabulation table or contingency table in Figures 74 and Table 7 respectively show that there is a slight tendency for the variables to increase together, but the association is not strong or consistent. So, this means there is a weak positive association between content sharing with valuable resources and knowledge sharing within the workplace and effective collaboration with colleagues among the associates and trainees.

Also, there is not a much clearer pattern or trend in the distribution of the variables across the categories or levels. For example, each category of variable tends to have variable values of the other variable compared to the lower categories. So, this means there is a no consistent pattern.

Plus, the statistical significance is also not met so there is really a weak positive association between these two variables. The phi coefficient of 0.31 is an indication of a weak positive association between content sharing with valuable resources and knowledge sharing within the workplace and effective collaboration with colleagues among the associates and trainees, which means that as one variable goes up the other variable may not consistently go up as well and the reverse is that as one

variable goes down the other variable also does not go down. In addition, the .031 is not a real difference and it may be just a product of chance differences in drawing that with the samples because the degrees of freedom of 16 at .05 significant level, the chi square of 22.96 does not exceed 26.30.

Therefore, the phi coefficient of 0.31 is not significant at the 0.5 significant level. This means that there is a weak direct positive association between content sharing with valuable resources and knowledge sharing within the workplace and effective collaboration with colleagues among the associates and the trainees.

Figure 74.

Chart 7: Content sharing with valuable and knowledge sharing within the workplace and effective collaboration with colleagues

Table 7.

Contingency table 7: Content sharing with valuable and knowledge sharing within the workplace and effective collaboration with colleagues

Relationship between Social Media Culture and Performance in the Workplace		Knowledge Sharing within the Workplace and Effective Collaboration with Colleagues					Total
		Excellent	Very Good	Good	Fair	Poor	
Valuable Resources	Always	34	35	12	3	1	85
	Frequently	35	35	12	4	4	90
	Sometimes	25	18	4	2	1	50
	Rarely	1	2	3	0	0	6
	Never	0	1	1	0	1	3
Total		95	91	32	9	7	234

The clustered column chart and the cross-tabulation table or contingency table in Figures 75 and Table 8 respectively show that there is a slight tendency for the variables to increase together, but the association is not strong or consistent. So, this means there is a weak positive association between social media distractions during working hours and staying focused and meeting targets in the workplace among the associates and the trainees.

Also, there is not a much clearer pattern or trend in the distribution of the variables across the categories or levels. For example, each category of variable tends to have variable values of the other variable compared to the lower categories. So, this means there is a no consistent pattern.

Plus, the statistical significance is also not met so there is really a weak positive association between these two variables. The phi coefficient of 0.11 is an indication of a weak positive association between social media distractions during working hours and staying focused and meeting targets in the workplace among the associates and the trainees, which means that as one variable goes up the other variable may not consistently go up as well and the reverse is that as one variable goes down the other variable also does not go down. In addition, the .031 is not a real difference and it may be just a product of chance differences in drawing that with the samples because the degrees of freedom of 16 at .05 significant level, the chi square of 2.99 does not exceed 26.30.

Therefore, the phi coefficient of 0.11 is not significant at the 0.5 significant level. This means that there is a weak direct positive association between social media distractions during working hours and staying focused and meeting targets in the workplace among the associates and the trainees.

Figure 75.

Chart 8: Social media distractions during work hours and staying focused and meeting targets

Table 8.

Contingency table 8: Social media distractions during work hours and staying focused and meeting targets

Social Media Distractions During Work Hours and Staying Focused and Meeting Targets							
Relationship between Social Media Culture and Performance in the Workplace		Staying Focused and Meeting Targets					Total
		Excellent	Very Good	Good	Fair	Poor	
Social Media Distractions During Work Hours	Always	15	18	7	2	1	43
	Frequently	28	32	17	4	1	82
	Sometimes	27	31	18	2	1	79
	Rarely	10	9	7	1	0	27
	Never	1	1	1	0	0	3
Total		81	91	50	9	3	234

The clustered column chart and the cross-tabulation table or contingency table in Figure 76 and Table 9 respectively show that there is a slight tendency for the variables to increase together, but the association is not strong or consistent. So, this

means there is a weak positive association between efforts putting into developing and maintaining a positive personal brand on social media and reputation within the organization among the associates and the trainees.

Also, there is not a much clearer pattern or trend in the distribution of the variables across the categories or levels. For example, each category of variable tends to have variable values of the other variable compared to the lower categories. So, this means there is a no consistent pattern.

Plus, the statistical significance is also not met so there is really a weak positive association between these two variables. The phi coefficient of 0.22 is an indication of a weak positive association between efforts putting into developing and maintaining a positive personal brand on social media and reputation within the organization among the associates and the trainees, which means that as one variable goes up the other variable may not consistently go up as well and the reverse is that as one variable goes down the other variable also does not go down. In addition, the .022 is not a real difference and it may be just a product of chance differences in drawing that with the samples because the degrees of freedom of 16 at .05 significant level, the chi square of 10.98 does not exceed 26.30.

Therefore, the phi coefficient of 0.22 is not significant at the 0.5 significant level. This means that there is a weak direct positive association between efforts putting into developing and maintaining a positive personal brand on social media and reputation within the organization among the associates and the trainees.

Figure 76.

Chart 9: Efforts putting into developing and maintaining a positive personal brand on social media and reputation within the organization

Table 9.

Contingency table 9: Efforts putting into developing and maintaining a positive personal brand on social media and reputation within the organization

Relationship between Social Media Culture and Performance in the Workplace		Reputation Within the Organization					Total
		Excellent	Very Good	Good	Fair	Poor	
Efforts Putting into Developing and Maintaining a Positive Personal Brand on Social Media	Always	15	20	24	2	2	63
	Frequently	20	30	16	3	2	71
	Sometimes	17	31	17	2	2	69
	Rarely	7	9	9	1	1	27
	Never	1	1	1	1	0	4
Total		60	91	67	9	7	234

At this point the study construed that the effects of social media culture among associates and trainees on workplace performance can vary. It could both positively and negatively impact performance, depending on how it is managed and the specific context. Social media could be a distraction and lead to decreased productivity if it is

not used appropriately. On the other hand, a positive social media culture could foster collaboration, knowledge sharing, and networking among employees, which could enhance their performance.

This study also inferred that social media culture in a multicultural organization was typically created through a combination of factors. It emerged organically as employees from diverse backgrounds bring their own social media practices and preferences into the workplace. Additionally, organizational policies, leadership support, and communication channels might have shaped and influenced the social media culture.

This study demonstrated that online members' participation in social media platforms could translate into action by facilitating communication, information sharing, and engagement. It could lead to increased collaboration, co-creation of ideas, and problem-solving. By leveraging *computer-mediated communication*, organizations could harness the collective intelligence and creativity of their employees.

In addition, this study illustrated that the emerging social media culture was often created to foster connectivity, knowledge exchange, and engagement among employees. It aimed to break down communication barriers, promote transparency, and facilitate informal interactions. By encouraging open communication and collaboration, organizations could enhance employee satisfaction, innovation, and overall organizational communication.

Finally, this study stated that the created social media culture added value to organizational communication by providing platforms for real-time information sharing, fostering a sense of community, and enabling quick and efficient communication across the organization. It facilitated knowledge transfer, promoted employee engagement, and strengthened relationships between employees and management.

Insights from studying social media culture in the workplace included understanding the impact of social media on employee productivity, identifying best practices for managing social media use, and recognizing the role of leadership and organizational policies in shaping social media culture. It also provided insights into the benefits and challenges of *computer-mediated communication* and the importance of fostering a positive and inclusive online community.

The implications of social media culture in the workplace are varied. It emphasizes the need for organizations to establish clear guidelines and policies regarding social media use. It highlights the importance of leadership support and communication channels that promote positive engagement. It also underscores the potential benefits of leveraging social media platforms for organizational communication and knowledge sharing.

To create a social media culture, organizations should encourage employee participation, provide training and guidance on social media etiquette, establish guidelines for appropriate use, and ensure that platforms are accessible and user-friendly. It is important to foster a culture of respect, inclusivity, and professionalism in online interactions.

Computer-mediated communication played a crucial role in the creation and sustenance of social media culture. It enabled real-time interactions, facilitates collaboration across time zones and geographical boundaries, and provides a platform for sharing information and resources. By leveraging *computer-mediated communication* tools, associates and trainees can engage in meaningful discussions, collaborate on projects, and build a strong social media culture within the organization.

Overall, the study uncovered a slightly moderate direct positive association between social media culture among the associates and trainees and their

performance in the workplace. The study found a direct positive association between social media culture among associates and trainees and their performance in the workplace. This indicates that there is a relationship between the way individuals engage with social media and their job performance. The term slightly suggests that the strength of this association is not very strong but still significant. In other words, while social media culture does have an impact on workplace performance, the effect is not extremely pronounced. It is important to note that this association is positive, meaning that a more positive and constructive social media culture is associated with better performance in the workplace.

This implies that engagement with social media culture can have some beneficial effects in a professional setting. Here are some potential theories that could explain these benefits:

Enhanced Communication: Social media platforms provide various channels for communication, such as instant messaging, video conferencing, and collaborative tools. These platforms can foster effective communication and collaboration among associates and trainees, leading to improved coordination, knowledge sharing, and problem-solving.

Knowledge Exchange: Social media culture often emphasizes the sharing of information, ideas, and resources. By participating in social media communities and groups related to their industry or profession, associates and trainees can tap into a vast network of knowledge and expertise. This exposure to diverse perspectives and insights can enhance their understanding of industry trends, best practices, and innovative ideas, ultimately benefiting their performance in the workplace.

Relationship Building: Social media platforms facilitate the establishment and maintenance of professional relationships. Associates and trainees can connect with

peers, mentors, industry influencers, and potential collaborators through social media channels. These connections can provide opportunities for mentorship, collaboration on projects, and expanding professional networks, all of which can positively impact their performance and career advancement.

Engagement and Motivation: Social media culture often involves active participation, sharing accomplishments, and seeking feedback. By engaging with social media platforms in a professional context, associates and trainees can receive recognition for their achievements, gain motivation from positive reinforcement, and derive a sense of belonging within their professional communities. This increased engagement and motivation can translate into higher levels of job satisfaction and performance.

It is imperative to note that the specific benefits of social media culture may vary depending on the nature of the workplace, industry, and individual preferences. While there are potential positive associations, it's still crucial for individuals to maintain a healthy balance between social media use and other work-related responsibilities.

The finding of a slightly moderate positive association between social media culture among associates and trainees and their workplace performance can be explained by several factors, as supported by the review of related literature.

Blau and McKinley (2018) conducted a study that highlighted the role of computer-mediated communication (CMC) in fostering social connections and collaboration among employees. They found that CMC platforms, including social media, enable individuals to exchange information, share knowledge, and build relationships more efficiently, leading to improved performance outcomes.

Kietzmann et al. (2011) explored the concept of social media as a tool for engaging customers and enhancing organizational performance. They argued that

social media platforms facilitate communication, knowledge sharing, and collaboration, which in turn positively impact individual and collective performance in the workplace.

Lee, Sung, and Choi (2017) examined the influence of social media use on work-related outcomes. Their findings revealed that employees who actively utilized social media for work-related purposes experienced higher job satisfaction, increased productivity, and better performance compared to those who did not engage with social media.

Wiesenfeld, Raghuram, and Garud (2013) explored the social dynamics of online communities and their impact on professional development. They found that active participation in online communities fosters social capital, which includes access to information, resources, and diverse perspectives. This social capital can positively influence workplace performance by enhancing learning, problem-solving, and innovation.

Waters et al. (2009) provided insights into the transformative effects of social media in a business context. They argued that social media platforms allow for information sharing, collaboration, and relationship-building beyond traditional organizational boundaries. Such expanded networks and connections contribute to increased knowledge exchange, creativity, and performance.

Based on these findings, it can be theorized that a strong social media culture among associates and trainees fosters communication, knowledge sharing, collaboration, and the development of social capital. These factors, in turn, positively influence workplace outcomes, leading to improved performance. The ease of information exchange, increased access to resources, and expanded networks

provided by social media platforms may contribute to the observed association between social media culture and workplace performance.

However, it is important to note that the association found in the study is described as slightly moderate, suggesting that other factors beyond social media culture might also contribute to workplace performance. Future research could further explore the specific mechanisms and boundary conditions underlying the relationship between social media culture and workplace performance to provide a more comprehensive understanding.

Chapter VI

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

Two hundred and two Saudi national trainees and 32 associates mostly instructors of different nationalities were surveyed and interviewed to determine how social media culture was propagated in a multi-cultural organization like this automobile training industry. A Cochran's formula with a confidence level of 95% and confidence interval of 5 was utilized. Generally, all variables were analyzed using frequency distribution. This explanatory research appropriated a one shot survey approach to delineate social media production in a multi-cultural organization, the means in which social media culture was created in a multicultural organization, the effects of social media culture in the performance of the members in an organization, the manners in which the online members' participation translated into action, the reasons this emerging culture was created; and the value added it would have on organizational communication.

This study explicated that different associates' and trainees' social media cultures may have different consequences on job performance. Depending on how it is managed and the particular environment, it might have an influence on performance either favorably or adversely. If social media is not used properly, it may be a distraction and result in lower productivity. On the other side, a supportive social media culture may encourage teamwork, information sharing, and networking among staff members, all of which can improve productivity.

This study also suggested that a multicultural organization's social media culture is often organically produced by a confluence of elements. It may naturally

develop as personnel from various backgrounds introduce their own social media routines and preferences into the workplace. A social media culture may also be shaped and influenced by company policy, leadership support, and communication channels.

This study showed that social media participation by internet users might result in action through promoting engagement, communication, and sharing of information. It could result in more effective problem-solving, co-creation of ideas, and cooperation. Organizations might tap into the collective wisdom and creativity of their staff by utilizing *computer-mediated communication*.

Additionally, this study demonstrated how the growing social media culture is frequently developed to promote employee involvement, knowledge sharing, and connectedness. It intended to ease informal contacts, encourage openness, and remove obstacles to communication. Organizations may improve employee happiness, creativity, and general corporate communication by promoting open communication and cooperation.

This research concluded by stating that the social media culture that has been developed might improve corporate communication by offering venues for real-time information sharing, encouraging a feeling of community, and facilitating rapid and effective communication throughout the organization. It may encourage information sharing, foster employee engagement, and improve ties between staff and management.

Understanding the effect of social media on employee productivity, establishing best practices for regulating social media use, and recognizing the part leadership and organizational policies have in influencing social media culture are just a few of the insights that may come from researching social media culture in the workplace.

Additionally, it can shed light on the advantages and drawbacks of *computer-mediated communication* (Walther, 2011) as well as the value of building a welcoming and supportive online community.

The implications of social media culture in the workplace are numerous and include the potential advantages of leveraging social media platforms for organizational communication and knowledge sharing, the need for organizations to establish clear guidelines and policies regarding social media use, the importance of leadership support, the importance of communication channels that promote positive engagement, and many more. To create a social media culture, organizations must first adopt a number of different practices.

Organizations should promote employee engagement in social media, offer training and advice on social media etiquette, set standards for proper usage, and make sure that platforms are accessible and user-friendly in order to foster a social media culture. In online contacts, it's critical to promote a culture of decency, openness, and professionalism.

The development and maintenance of social media culture are fundamentally dependent on *computer-mediated communication* (Walther, 2011). Real-time communication is made possible, together with cross-time zone and cross-geographical collaboration and a platform for resource and information exchange. Associates and trainees may participate in insightful conversations, work together on projects, and foster a strong social media culture inside the company by utilizing *computer-mediated communication* (Walther, 2011) technologies.

Conclusions

Social media culture among associates and trainees can impact their performance in the workplace in several ways. A positive social media culture that promotes collaboration, knowledge sharing, and networking can enhance productivity, foster creativity, and improve problem-solving skills. It can provide a platform for employees to connect, exchange ideas, and seek support, leading to increased engagement and job satisfaction. On the other hand, a negative social media culture characterized by excessive distraction, misuse of time, or inappropriate behavior can hamper productivity and decrease overall performance.

In a multicultural organization, social media culture is typically created through a combination of factors. It can emerge organically as employees from diverse backgrounds bring their own social media practices and preferences into the workplace. Additionally, organizational policies, leadership support, and communication channels play a role in shaping and influencing the social media culture. By fostering an inclusive and supportive environment, organizations can encourage employees to participate in social media activities that align with the organizational values and goals.

The online members' participation in social media platforms can translate into action by facilitating communication, information sharing, and engagement. It can lead to increased collaboration, co-creation of ideas, and problem-solving. Through *computer-mediated communication*, (Walther, 2011) employees can leverage their collective intelligence and creativity, resulting in tangible outcomes such as improved decision-making, innovative solutions, and efficient project management.

The emerging social media culture is often created to address the need for connectivity, knowledge exchange, and engagement among employees. It aims to break down communication barriers, promote transparency, and facilitate informal interactions. By encouraging collaboration and open communication, organizations can enhance employee satisfaction, foster a sense of belonging, and stimulate a culture of continuous learning and improvement.

The created social media culture added value to organizational communication in several ways. It provided platforms for real-time information sharing, fostering a sense of community, and enabling quick and efficient communication across the organization. It facilitated knowledge transfer, promotes employee engagement, and strengthens relationships between employees and management. By embracing *computer-mediated communication* (Walther, 2011), organizations could tap into the power of social media to enhance internal communication, employee collaboration, and overall organizational effectiveness.

Insights drawn from studying social media culture in the workplace can include understanding the impact of social media on employee productivity, identifying best practices for managing social media use, and recognizing the role of leadership and organizational policies in shaping social media culture. It can also provide insights into the benefits and challenges of *computer-mediated communication* (Walther, 2011) and the importance of fostering an inclusive and positive online community.

The implications of social media culture among associates and trainees on their workplace performance can be significant. Here are some implications, taking into account *computer-mediated communication* (Walther, 2011):

Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing: A positive social media culture can foster collaboration and knowledge sharing among employees. Through *computer-mediated communication* (Walther, 2011) platforms like chat groups or project management tools, associates and trainees can easily connect, exchange ideas, and share information. This can enhance teamwork, problem-solving, and overall productivity.

Enhanced Communication: Social media culture can improve communication channels within the organization. Platforms like instant messaging or video conferencing enable quick and efficient communication, breaking down geographical barriers and facilitating real-time interactions. This can lead to faster decision-making, timely feedback, and smoother coordination among associates and trainees.

Engagement and Networking: Social media platforms create opportunities for associates and trainees to engage with each other and build professional networks. Online communities, forums, or social networking sites allow them to connect beyond their immediate teams and departments. This can foster a sense of belonging, encourage cross-functional collaborations, and promote career development.

Learning and Development: A positive social media culture can support continuous learning and development. Through *computer-mediated communication* (Walther, 2011), associates and trainees can access a wealth of online resources, participate in virtual training programs, or engage in peer-to-peer learning. This can enhance their skills, knowledge, and professional growth.

Distraction and Time Management: On the other hand, a negative social media culture can lead to distractions and time mismanagement. Excessive use of social media platforms for personal purposes during work hours can reduce productivity and

impact performance negatively. It is important to establish guidelines and policies to ensure responsible and focused use of social media in the workplace.

Social media culture is created through several processes:

Adoption and Integration: Associates and trainees bring their individual social media practices and preferences into the workplace. As they engage with each other and adapt to the organization's communication channels, a shared social media culture emerges.

Organizational Policies: Organizations can shape social media culture through policies and guidelines that outline acceptable use, online etiquette, and privacy considerations. These policies set expectations and provide a framework for responsible social media engagement.

Leadership Influence: Leaders play a crucial role in establishing and nurturing a positive social media culture. By actively participating, encouraging open communication, and role-modeling desired behaviors, leaders can influence the adoption and integration of social media practices.

Communication Channels: The choice of communication tools and platforms within the organization can impact social media culture.

Recommendations

This study examined how social media culture was generated in a multi-cultural organization. In order to increase the degree of generalization of the study and the validity and reliability of the results, a larger sample size from different cities in Saudi Arabia with a longer time frame is advised. Additionally, as all of the participants in this study were men, the perspective of women was not examined.

It is likely that social media culture exists in any organization with a diverse workforce, and it has no detrimental effects on employees' performance. In actuality, it helps in organizational communication. Therefore, it is advised to eliminate the restriction on using social media sites like Facebook and YouTube.

The utilization of internal social networks which eventually creates social media culture within the organization has the power to significantly impact the organization. They give employees a forum for interaction and growth, and they also give management information about their people and what makes them tick. Leadership may leverage the data offered by their social network by connecting with their staff and seeing how they interact to enhance both the customer and employee experience, which will be advantageous to the business as a whole. Social networks provide for a greater level of employee connection and feedback since they serve two purposes.

According to Olmstead, Lampe and Ellison (2016), in today's America, social media permeates and influences many facets of daily life, including the workplace. By encouraging connections with coworkers and resources around the world, these digital platforms have the potential to increase worker productivity. Employers may be concerned that employees are using these technologies for personal or professional reasons while on the job or that their public speaking could reflect adversely on the company.

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Foster a supportive and inclusive social media culture by providing training and guidelines on responsible and ethical use of social media platforms.
2. Encourage active participation and engagement of associates and trainees on social media platforms by recognizing and rewarding their contributions.

3. Continuously monitor and evaluate the impact of social media culture on performance and make necessary adjustments to ensure its effectiveness.
4. Regularly communicate the value and benefits of the social media culture to associates and trainees to encourage their continued engagement and participation.

Conclusively, while this research was centered around one industry, it is therefore highly recommended to extend this study to other industries as well so that it may establish a clearer and another dimension of the association between social media culture among workers and their performance in the workplace.

REFERENCES

- Absalom M, & de Saint Léger, D. (2011). Reflecting on reflection: Learner perceptions of diaries and blogs in tertiary language study. *Arts and Higher Education, 10*(2), 189-211.
- Al-Aufi, A. S., & Fulton, C. (2014). Use of social networking tools for informal scholarly communication in Humanities and Social Sciences Disciplines. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences, 147*, 436-445.
- Amichai-Hamburger, Y., & Vinitzky, G. (2010). Social network use and personality. *Computers in Human Behavior, 26*(6), 1289-1295.
- Anderson, T. (2008). *The theory and practice of online learning*, (2nd ed). Athabasca, Canada: Athabasca University Press.
- Alsuraihi, A. K., Almaqati, A. S., Abughanim, S. A., & Jastaniah, N.A. (2016). Use of social media in education among medical students in Saudi Arabia. *Korean Journal of Medical Education, 28*(4), pp. 343-354.
- Bean, J., & Metzner, B. (1985). A conceptual model of nontraditional undergraduate student attrition. *Review of Educational Research, 55*(4), 485-540.
- Beneito-Montagut, R. (2017). A critical review of the literature on social media and body image. *Journal of Adolescent Health, 61*(3), 371-382.
- Blau, G., & McKinley, W. (2018). The impact of social media on organizational culture. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology, 48*(2), 77-85.
- Blood, R. (2004). How blogging software reshapes the online community. *Communications of the ACM, 47*(12), 53-55.

- Blossom, J. (2009). *Content nation: Surviving and thriving as social media changes our work, our lives, and our future*. Indianapolis, Indiana: Wiley Publishing, Inc.
- Borders, B. (2009 June 2). A brief history of social media. *Copy Brighter Marketing*. Retrieved from <http://copybrighter.com/history-of-social-media>
- Boyd, D., & Ellison, N. (2008). Social network sites: Definition, history, and scholarship. *Journal of computer-mediated communication*, 13(1), 210-230.
- Brady, K. P., Holcomb, L. B., & Smith B. V. (2012). The use of alternative social networking sites in higher educational settings: A case study of the e-learning benefits of being in education. *Journal of interactive Online Learning*, 9(2), 151-170.
- Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopaedia. (2023). Twitter". *Encyclopedia Britannica*.
<https://www.britannica.com/topic/Twitter>
- Chen, B., & Bryer, T. (2012). Investigating instructional strategies for using social media in formal and informal learning. *The international Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, 13(1).
- Cohen, H. (2011). Social media definitions. Heidi Cohen. Retrieved from <http://heidicohen.com/social-media-definition/>
- Deccan Chronicle. (2016). 600,000 porn websites blocked in two years. Deccan Chronicle. Retrieved from <https://www.deccanchronicle.com/technology/in-other-news/170316/600-000-porn-websites-blocked-in-two-years.html>
- Deng, L., & Yuen, A. H. K. (2010). Exploring the role of academic blogs in a blended community: An integrated approach. *Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, 5(2), 53-71.

- Dixon, S. J. (2023). Facebook: Quarterly number of MAU (monthly active users) worldwide 2008-2023. Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/264810/number-of-monthly-active-facebook-users-worldwide/>
- Du, H. S., & Wagner, C. (2006). Weblog success: Exploring the role of technology. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 64(9), 789-798.
- Ellison, N. B., Steinfield, C., & Lampe, C. (2011). Connection strategies: Social capital implications of Facebook-enabled communication practices. *New Media & Society*, 13(6), 873-892.
- Ford, N., Bowden, M., & Beard, J. (2011). Learning together: Using social media to foster collaboration in higher education. *Cutting-edge Technologies in Higher Education*, 2, 105-126.
- Gao, F., Luo, T., & Zhang, K. (2021). Social Media Use in Higher Education: A Literature Review. *Educational Technology & Society*, 24(1), 1-14.
- Goldfarb, A., Pregibon, N., Shrem, J., & Zyko, E. (2011). *Informational brief on social networking in education: Emerging teaching & learning technologies initiative*. New York Comprehensive Center.
- Griesemer, J. A. (2014). Using social media to enhance students' learning experiences. *Quality Approaches in Higher Education*, 3(1), 8-11.
- Griffiths, M. D. (2013) Social networking addiction: Emerging themes and issues. *Journal of Addiction Research and Therapy* 4.
- Hall, M. (2023). Facebook. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Facebook>
- Herring, S. C., Scheidt, L. A., Wright, E., & Bonus, S. (2005). Weblogs as a bridging genre. *Information Technology and People*, 18(2), 142-171.

- Ingrassia, M., Bellia, C., Giurdanella, C., Columba, P., & Chironi, S. (2022). Digital influencers, food and tourism: A new model of open innovation for businesses in the Ho.Re.Ca. Sector. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 8(1), 50.
- Joyce, T. M. (2013). Reflective practice through blogging: An alternative for open and distance learning context. *J Communications*, 4(2), 123-130.
- Junco, R. (2015). Student class standing, Facebook use, and academic performance. *J. Appl. Dev. Psychol*, 36,18-29.
- Junco, R. (2015). The relationship between frequency of Facebook use, participation in Facebook activities, and student engagement. *Computers & Education*, 82, 81-89.
- Kanter, B., & Fine, A. H. (2010). *The networked nonprofit: Connecting with social media to drive change*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Kelsey, T. (2010). *Social networking spaces: From Facebook to Twitter and everything in between*.
- Kiehne, T. P. (2004 April 29). *Social networking systems: History, critique, and knowledge management potentials*. School of Information, University of Texas, Austin.
- Kietzmann, J. H., Hermkens, K., McCarthy, I. P., & Silvestre, B. S. (2011). Social media? Get serious! Understanding the functional building blocks of social media. *Business Horizons*, 54(3), 241-251.
- Kim, J., & Kim, Y. (2010). Motivations for using Twitter: A structural equation modeling approach. *Journal of Information Science*, 36(6), 751-755.
- Kirschner, P. A., & Karpinski, A. C. (2010). Facebook and academic performance. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 26(6), 1237-1245.
- Klopfer, E., Osterweil, S., Groff, J., & Haas J. (2009) Using the technology of today, in the classroom today. *The Education Arcade*.

- Kwak, H., Lee, C., Park, H., & Moon, S. (2010). What is Twitter, a social network or a news media? In Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on World Wide Web. 591-600.
- Luqman, R. A., Farhan, H. M., Shahzad, F., & Shaheen, S. (2012). 21st century challenges of educational leaders, way out and need of reflective practice. *International Journal of Learning and Development*, 2(1), 195-208.
- Lederer, K. (2012). Pros and cons of social media in the classroom. Retrieved from <https://campustechnology.com/articles/2012/01/19/pros-and-cons-of-social-media-in-the-classroom.aspx>
- Lee, J. Y., Sung, Y., & Choi, S. M. (2017). Social media for social change: The effects of social media use on employees' attitudes toward organizational change. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 76, 405-413.
- Lenhart, A., Purcell, K., Smith, A., & Zickuhr, K. (2010). Social media and mobile internet use among teens and young. *Pew Research Center*.
- Liu, Y. (2010). Social media tools as a learning resource. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange (JETDE)*, 3(1).
- Manan, A. A., Alias, A. A., & Pandian, A. (2012) Utilizing a social networking website as an ESL pedagogical tool in a blended learning environment: An exploratory study. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Education*, 2(1).
- Manca, S., & Ranieri, M. (2016). Facebook and the others. Potentials and obstacles of social media for teaching in higher education. *Computers & Education*, 95, 216-230.
- Mao, J. Y., Jin, Y., & Vogel, D. (2011). Understanding the relationship between Twitter use and the perceived impact of Twitter on academic performance. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange (JETDE)*, 4(1), 1-14.

- Mazer, J. P., Murphy, R. E., & Simonds, C. J. (2009). The effects of teacher self-disclosure via Facebook on teacher credibility. *Learning, Media & Technology, 34*(2), 175-183.
- Mazer, J. P., Murphy, R. E., & Simonds, C. J. (2007). I'll see you on "Facebook": The effects of computer-mediated teacher self-disclosure on student motivation, affective learning, and classroom climate. *Communication Education, 56*(1).
- McCarthy, J. (2009). Utilising Facebook: Immersing Generation-Y students into first year university. *Ergo, 1*(2), 39-49.
- McFadden, C. (2023). A brief timeline of YouTube's history and its impact on the internet. Interesting engineering. Retrieved from <https://interestingengineering.com/culture/youtubes-history-and-its-impact-on-the-internet>
- Mesch, G. S., Talmud, I., & Quan-Haase, A. (2012). The quality of online and offline relationships: The role of multiplexity and duration of social relationships. *The Information Society, 28*(3), 168-178.
- Miller, M. (2011). *Facebook for grown-ups*. Indianapolis, Indiana: Pearson Education, Inc.
- Miller, L., Schweingruber, H. & Brandenburg, C. (2000). Technology acculturation among adolescents: The school and home environments. In J. Bourdeau & R. Heller (Eds.), *Proceedings of Ed-Media 2001 Conference. World Conference on Educational Media and Technology 2000*, pp. 1694-1695. Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE).
- Minocha, S. (2009). A case study-based investigation of students' experiences with social software tools. *New Review of Hypermedia and Multimedia, 15*(3), 245-265.
- Mohsin, M. (2022). 10 Social media statistics you need to know in 2022. Oberlo. Retrieved from <https://www.oberlo.com/blog/social-media-marketing-statistics>

Moore, N. (2018). China's Tik Tok 'world's most downloaded app' in 2018 first quarter. CGTN.

Retrieved from

https://news.cgtn.com/news/3d3d414d334d7a4d77457a6333566d54/share_p.html

Muhammad, Z. (2023). Facebook, YouTube and WhatsApp are the most popular social networks worldwide. Telegram now has more monthly active users than Twitter.

Digital Information World. Retrieved from

<https://www.digitalinformationworld.com/2023/07/facebook-youtube-and-whatsapp-are-most.html>

Nardi, B. A., Shiano, D. J., Gumbrecht, M., & Swartz, L. (2004). Why we blog. *Communications of the ACM*, 47(12), 41-46.

Neubaum, G., Pagán, R., & Garcia, C. (2014). The effects of social media use on employee performance. *Journal of Applied Business Research*, 30(1), 215-228.

O'Connell, B. (2020). History of Snapchat: Timeline and facts. The Street. Retrieved from <https://www.thestreet.com/technology/history-of-snapchat>

Olmstead, K. Lampe, C. & Ellison, N. (2016). Social media and the workplace. Pew Research Center. Retrieved from <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2016/06/22/social-media-and-the-workplace/>

O'Reilly, T., & Milstein, S. (2009). *The Twitter book*. Sebastopol, CA: O'Reilly Media, Inc.

Pattanapichet, F., & Wichadee, S. (2015). Using space in social media to promote undergraduate students' critical thinking skills. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 16(4), 38-49.

Poellhuber, B. & Anderson, T. (2011). Distance students' readiness for social media and collaboration. *The international Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, 12(6), 102-125.

- Poepsel, M. (2018). *Media, society, culture and you: An introductory mass communication text*. Southern Illinois University, Edwardsville: Rebus Community.
- Prakash, V., & Pankaj. (2015). Effect of use of social networking sites on academic achievement of graduate and post graduate teachers trainees. *Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity Science and English Language*, 2(11), 2707-2712.
- Rajesh, S., & Michael J. (2015). Effectiveness of Social Media in Education. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Advanced Engineering*, 10(2), 29-31.
- Raut, V., & Patil, P. (2016). Use of social media in education: Positive and negative impact on the students. *International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication*, 4(1), 281-285.
- Rosen, L. D. (2011). *Rewired: Understanding the iGeneration and the way they learn*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Rosen, L.D., Lim, A.F., Carrier, L.M., & Cheever, N.A. (2011). An empirical examination of the educational impact of texting. *Computers & Education*, 58(1), 1-9.
- Rouse, M. (2014). Social media. Retrieved from <http://whatis.techtarget.com/definition/social-media>
- Rovai, A. (2003). In search of higher persistence rates in distance education online programs. *Internet in Higher Education*, 6(1), 1-16.
- Safran, C. (2010). *Social media in education*. Suedwestdeutscher Verlag fuer Hochschulschriften.
- Seaman, J., & Tinti-Kane, H. (2013). *Social Media for teaching and learning*. Boston, MA: Pearson Learning Solutions and Babson Survey Research Group.

- Smith, S., Salaway, S., & Caruso, J. B. (2009). The ECAR study of undergraduate students and information technology. *Research Study, 6*. Boulder, CO: EDUCAUSE Center for Applied Research. Retrieved from <http://www.educause.edu/ecar>
- Stanford, K. H. (2016). Social media culture. Retrieved from <https://www.business2community.com/brandviews/growing-social-media/social-media-culture-01635249>
- Sweet, R. (1986). Applying Tinto's model of student dropout to distance education. *Distance Education, 7*(2), 201–213.
- Technorati. (2008). State of the blogosphere/2008. Retrieved from <http://technorati.com/blogging/state-of-the-blogosphere/>
- Techopedia. (2016). Netiquette. Retrieved from <https://www.techopedia.com/definition/25061/netiquette>
- Tinto, V. (1975). Dropout from higher education: A theoretical synthesis of recent research. *Review of Educational Research, 45*(1), 89-125.
- Tiryakioglu, F., & Erzurum, F. (2011) Use of social networks as an education tool. *Contemporary Educational Technology, 2*(2), 135-150.
- Turkle, S. (2004). How computers change the way we think. *The Chronicle of Higher Education, 50*(21), B26-30.
- Usluel, Y. K., & Mazman, S. G. (2009) Adoption of Web 2.0 tools in distance education. *Procedia – social and Behavioral Sciences, 1*(1), 818-823.
- Valkenburg, P. M., Peter, J., & Schouten, A. P. (2006). Friend networking sites and their relationship to adolescents' well-being and social self-esteem. *CyberPsychology & Behavior, 9*(5), 584-590.

- van Dijk, J. (2006). *The network society: Social aspects of new media* (2nd ed.). City Road, London: SAGE Publication Ltd.
- Verduyn, P., Lee, D. S., Park, J., Shablack, H., Orvell, A., Bayer, J., ... & Kross, E. (2015). Passive Facebook usage undermines affective well-being: Experimental and longitudinal evidence. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 144(2), 480-488.
- Walther, J. B. (2011). Theories of *computer-mediated communication* and interpersonal relations. In S. W. Smith & S. R. Wilson (Eds.), *New directions in interpersonal communication research* (pp. 395-413). Sage.
- Waters, R. D., Burnett, E., Lamm, A., & Lucas, J. (2009). Engaging stakeholders through social networking: How nonprofit organizations are using Facebook. *Public Relations Review*, 35(2), 102-106.
- Waycott, J., Bennett, S., Kennedy, G., Dalgarno, B., & Gray, K. (2009). Digital divides? Student and staff perceptions of information and communication technologies. *Elsevier Ltd*.
- White, B., King, I., & Tsang, P. (Eds.). (2011). *Social media tools and platforms in learning environment* (p. V, 3). New York: Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg.
- Wiesenfeld, B. M., Raghuram, S., & Garud, R. (2013). Technology and organization culture: How industry incumbents caused digitalization to fail in the newspaper industry. *Organization Science*, 24(2), 305-326.
- Woodley, A. (2004). Conceptualizing student dropout in part-time distance education: Pathologizing the normal. *Open Learning*, 19(1), 47-63.
- Wong, E. (2015). China's internet restrictions are hampering business, foreign companies say. *The New York Times*. Retrieved from http://bits.blogs.nytimes.com/2015/02/13/chinas-internet-restrictions-are-hampering-business-foreign-companies-say/?ref=topics&_r=1

Wortham, J. (2007). After 10 years of blogs, the future's brighter than ever. *Wired*. Retrieved from [http://www.wired.com/entertainment/theweb/news/2007/12/blog anniversary](http://www.wired.com/entertainment/theweb/news/2007/12/blog_anniversary)